

GREENGAGE

ENGAGING CITIZENS - MOBILIZING TECHNOLOGY - DELIVERING GREEN DEAL

Smart governance models 2

Work Package 2, Deliverable D2.5

AWAITING VALIDATION BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

Smart governance models 2

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List of Acronyms

CO	Citizen Observatory
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
EU	European Union
GEOSS	Global Earth Observation System of Systems
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
KM	Kilometer
LCWIP	Local Cycling and Walking Infrastructure Plan
WECA	West of England Combined Authority
GPS	Global Positioning System
DNSH	Do No Significant Harm
ISO	International Organisation for Standardization
PNRR	National Recovery and Resilience Plan
BUAS	Breda University of Applied Sciences
PNB	Province of North Brabant
MPA	Miljøpunkt Amager

CEMR	Council for European Municipalities and Regions
ICLEI	International Council for Local Environmental Initiatives

Glossary

Citizen Observatory	According to WeObserve, “Citizen Observatories (COs) are community-based environmental monitoring and information systems, that invite individuals to share observations, typically via mobile phone or the web. Throughout these activities citizens become able to participate in environmental management/local governance.” [Reference: D2.1 - GREENGAGE Methodological Framework]
Citizen Science	“In Citizen Science, a broad network of people collaborates. Participants provide experimental data and facilities for researchers, raise new questions and co-create a new scientific culture. While they add value, volunteers acquire new learning and skills and gain a deeper understanding of the scientific work in appealing ways. As a result of this open, networked and transdisciplinary scenario, science-society-policy interactions are improved, leading in turn to a more democratic research, based on evidence and informed decision-making” (Socientize consortium, 2014, p. 10).
Smart Governance Model	Smart Governance is the process of governance that utilises modern technologies and ICT for collaborative, participatory, and transparent governance. A Smart Governance model encourages collaboration between government and Citizens and encourages innovation to improve cities’ operations.
Liveable neighbourhood	A liveable neighbourhood is the formal term applied to the “15 minute city” concept of planning, as applied in Bristol. This provides for easy access to daily necessities and services, such as education, leisure and shopping, by cycling, walking or public transport, by encouraging high density development, mixed land use and alternatives to the private car.
Innovation Pilots	GREENGAGE innovation pilots aim to promote co-created Citizen Observatories as part of a participatory governance process. They demonstrate how top-down urban planning processes can actively intermediate these novel bottom-up processes of multi-stakeholder engagement. The innovation pilots respond to the GREENGAGE mission to define and deliver Citizen Observatories as integral components of decision-making processes that address current urban and regional planning challenges of climate mitigation and adaptation as well as healthy cities. The five GREENGAGE innovation pilots will be co-designed and fully demonstrated in Bristol (the United Kingdom), Copenhagen (Denmark), Turano/Gerace (Italy) and the region of Noord Brabant (the Netherlands). [Reference: D2.1 - GREENGAGE Methodological Framework]
Bottom-up approach on citizen science and co-creation	The GREENGAGE Innovation Action is building on a bottom-up logic on co-creation, participatory research and citizen science. We propose to draw on the established approach of Extreme Citizen Science (ExCiteS) to approach science-based, community-led policy innovation towards strong sustainability. [Reference: D2.1 - GREENGAGE Methodological Framework]
Top-down approach on policy innovation	The GREENGAGE Innovation Action is informed by a top-down logic. That means the developed frameworks are setting boundaries for meaningful experimentation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The ethical framework is defining procedures on how to apply ethics in GREENGAGE COs. - The governance framework is defining the metrics through which the innovation potential of pilots will be captured - The methodological framework is setting core concepts and guides the development of the GREENGAGE approach on COs - The citizen science methodology frames how CO campaigns will be co-designed and co-delivered through exploring and exploiting existing technologies in piloting COs. [Reference: D2.1 - GREENGAGE Methodological Framework]

Executive summary (publishable)

This document presents the second version of Smart Governance Models, building on work set out in the initial version (D2.4) submitted in M3. It provides an update on the specifications of the innovation pilots and outlines the existing governance models applied in the pilot areas. The aim is to analyse and model the governance processes implemented by the pilot cities and villages, highlighting how GREENGAGE Citizen Observatories can support top-down and bottom-up participatory mechanisms. These models contribute valuable inputs to agenda setting, policy making and decision making at local level. This extended version enriches the first release with a comprehensive literature review on engagement, multi-level governance and data driven policy. It frames the climate change challenges confronted by the Green Deal as a “wicked issue” to convey their unique complexity. It outlines a “systems thinking” approach to governance to capture better the holistic, multi-level engagement required. It explores the potential of Citizen Observatories to provide the participative dimension of a systemic approach. It concludes that these have great potential to enhance decision making and participative governance, if citizens are suitably empowered and resource invested in maintaining public motivation. This document also serves as the theoretical foundation of the smart governance model to be proposed within GREENGAGE’s White Book (D6.8) due in M36.

Related documents

- Deliverable D1.9 – Ethics Management Plan and Activities 1
- Deliverable D1.10 - Ethics Management Plan and Activities 2
- Deliverable D1.11 - Data Management Plan 1
- Deliverable D1.12 - Data Management Plan 2
- Deliverable D2.1 - GREENGAGE CO Methodological Framework
- Deliverable D2.2 - Use Cases and Requirements Analysis 1
- Deliverable D2.3 – Use Cases and Requirements Analysis 2
- Deliverable D2.4 - Smart Governance Models 1
- Deliverable D4.1 - GREEN Engine and manual 1
- Deliverable D4.2 – GREEN Engine and manual 2
- Deliverable D5.1 – Piloting and Citizen Observer Activities Report 1
- Deliverable D6.7 – GREENGAGE based Citizen Observatory – White Book for PA 1

1 GREENGAGE summary

The pan-European Innovation Action, funded under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme, aims to promote innovative governance processes, and help public authorities in shaping their climate mitigation and adaptation policies. To achieve this aim, the GREENGAGE project will leverage citizens' participation and equip them with innovative digital solutions that will transform citizen's engagement and cities' effectiveness in delivering the European Green Deal objectives for carbon neutral cities.

Focusing on mobility, air quality and healthy living, citizens will be inspired to observe and co-create their cities by sensing their urban environments. The aim is to complement, validate, and enrich information in authoritative data held by the public administrations and public agencies. This will be facilitated by engaging with citizens to co-create green initiatives and to develop Citizen Observatories (CO). In GREENGAGE, Citizen Observatories will be a place where pilot cities will co-examine environmental issues integrating novel bottom-up process with top-down perspectives. This will provide the basis to co-create and co-design innovative solutions to monitor environmental problems at ground level with the help of citizens.

With two interrelated project dimensions, the project aims to enhance intelligence applied to city decision-making processes and governance by engaging with citizen observations integrated with Copernicus, Global Earth Observation System of Systems GEOSS, In-situ, and socio-economic intelligence, and by delivering innovative governance models based on novel toolboxes of decision-making methodologies and technologies.

The envisioned Citizen Observatories campaigns will be deployed and fully demonstrated in 5 pilot engagements in selected European cities and regions including: Bristol (the United Kingdom), Copenhagen (Denmark), Turano and Gerace (Italy) and the region of North Brabant (the Netherlands). These innovation pilots aim to highlight the need for smart city governance by promoting citizen engagement, co-creation, as well as gathering new data which will complement existing datasets and evidence-based decision and policymaking.

Figure 1: Structure of project GREENGAGE.

2 Introduction

This report builds on Deliverable 2.4 “Smart Governance Models 1” which provided an initial understanding of GREENGAGE smart urban governance model options and the pathways to its development and adoption. This work forms the basis for GREENGAGE partners engagement in the development of an urban governance model incorporating and deploying the full potentials of Citizen Observatories in support of bottom-up engagement in urban planning decision-making process. This partner engagement has taken place over 30 months in the context of Work Package 2 – “Citizens Observatory Governance Framework, Stakeholder Engagement and Requirements Analysis” that amongst other objectives supports the definition of “a multidisciplinary Citizen Observatory methodological framework and city governance models that promotes inclusive and egalitarian approaches for citizen participation in citizen environmental monitoring”. Specifically, Task 2.4 Smart Urban Governance Model and Pathways to Adoption, modelled the governance processes followed by the GREENGAGE innovation pilots to identify how Citizen Observatories as part of a participatory governance can be effected through the application of GREENGAGE tools.

The methodological basis for this initial assessment of the smart urban governance model incorporating Citizen Observatories into the urban planning decision-making process drew on 20 years experiment by UWE partners in EU funded projects. These projects have promoted smart city and open governance integrating top-down and bottom-up engagement in urban planning decision-making process enabled by information and communication technology (ICT) solutions including Copernicus derived products. This wide experience has been developed in discussions with GREENGAGE project partners, and facilitated by several in-person and online meetings during 30 months of the project and focused on:

- Elaborating the principles of the governance model of open integrated and interoperable governance as a framework for the specification of pilot city governance process;
- Identifying existing basis of urban planning governance process regarding pilot activities in terms of operational considerations specified in planning policy cycle;
- Exploring pilot initiatives regarding top-down and bottom-up planning process and local initiatives and potentials regarding Citizen Observatories and other citizen engagement innovation process and action;
- Modelling governance process to identify in detail existing urban planning decision-making and implementation process and potentials for introduction of Citizen Observatories derived intelligence for each pilot, to identify gaps and the added value of input from GREENGAGE tools.

The present report incorporates new material informed by additional research, specifically:

- A comprehensive literature review on engagement, multi-level governance and data driven policy. This focuses on the potential for “systems thinking” to deliver a platform for climate change governance that is comprehensive, inclusive, and deliberative, plus the contribution of citizen science and Citizen Observatories to achieving these ideals.
- A survey to obtain inputs from a sample of European cities on approaches and experiences related to citizen participation, Citizen Observatories, and smart governance processes. It explores the nature and scope of citizen participation internationally, and the challenges and opportunities that this policy and practice presents.
- A process, set out in diagrammatic form, to assist policy makers to establish a Citizen Observatory in different local contexts.

Above all, this document serves as the theoretical foundation of the smart governance model to be proposed within GREENGAGE’s White Book (D6.8) due in M36.

2.1 EU Horizon Europe Call CL6–2022–Governance–01

The starting point for the specification of the GREENGAGE smart urban governance model are the provisions of the EU Horizon Europe call CL6–2022–Governance–01 which aims to promote innovative governance, environmental observations, and digital solutions in support of the European Green Deal.

The central argument of this EU call is that transformative changes such as those required within the Green Deal are dynamic processes that need appropriate governance. At the same time, to ensure

coordination and for collaborative decision-making, governance requires multiple channels and networks that provide readily available data and information coming from different sources. Research and innovation activities therefore aim at both:

- Experimenting with new ways to govern the transition process and modernising the governance, in particular by making information and knowledge available and accessible.
- Providing insights into institutional barriers such as lock-ins, path dependency, political and cultural inertia power imbalances and regulatory inconsistencies or weaknesses.

In respect of these twin aims the call argues that innovative governance taking advantage of the use, uptake, deployment, and exploitation of environmental observations including space-based, in-situ-based (air, sea, land) observation, and citizen observations, as well as digital solutions, is key for innovative governance models and a more science-based policy design, implementation and monitoring. Data and information obtained through Environmental Observation is of great value when delivering crucial information to support the Green Deal and the climate and ecological transition.

Integration of this information from different sources (space-based, airborne including drones, in-situ and citizens' observations) with other relevant data and knowledge while ensuring accessible, interoperable or deployable information, delivers information necessary for shaping the direction and the development of policies. The potential of the ongoing digital transformation, and its wider impacts, positive and negative, need to be better understood and monitored in view of future policy design and implementation, governance, and solution development. Knowledge and innovation systems are key drivers to enhance co-creation and thus speed up innovation and the take-up of results needed to achieve the Green Deal objectives and targets.

In this context the call targets contributions to the wide deployment of, and added value of, environmental observations, by improving the uptake and validation of data collected by citizens and by increasing citizen involvement and engagement. Central to this is support for citizen engagement, specifically the active role of citizens in the collection and use of data and information within the urban environment to complement the data and information collected through other means of observation (space-based, airborne, etc.). Thereby contributing to more comprehensive and available data and information of good quality to assess the state of the urban environment in support of the climate transition and urban resilience, shaping policies targeting the monitoring and greening of the urban environment, in addition to monitoring schemes already set out by public authorities at different levels (regional, national, European, even global). The call also recognizes that it is critical to ensure the validation and uptake of citizen observations for policy, through the development of toolboxes, containing tested methodologies, methods, and technologies.

Required Outcomes:

- More widespread participation of citizens, (e.g., new and/or existing associations/groupings of citizens observers) in the monitoring, observation, and protection of the urban environment, complementary to governmental measures;
- Greater availability of qualitative and quantitative in-situ data for long time series and better geographical coverage, contributing to the in-situ component of existing observation systems (such as Copernicus, European research infrastructures and GEOSS);
- Broader use of data and information collected by citizens in policy and research, with crowdsourcing and citizen observations acknowledged as valuable information complementary to authoritative observations;
- Increased use of existing toolkits and development of new toolboxes (methodologies, methods, technologies) for broad use, which could include the development of efficient passive sampling systems;
- Leveraged use of wearables for citizens and other low-cost technologies in the domain of environmental observation.

2.2 GREENGAGE Response to the Call

GREENGAGE 's vision promotes innovative governance and helps public authorities in shaping their climate mitigation and adaptation policies by engaging with citizens to co-create green initiatives and to

develop Citizen Observatories, focusing on mobility, air quality and healthy living supporting the delivery of climate change mitigation (Figure 2).

GREENGAGE aims to achieve this vision by facilitating citizens to observe and co-create urban planning solutions by sensing urban environments complementing, validating, and enriching information held by the public administrations derived from remote sensing data and obtained via other authoritative observations. This enhanced and evidence-based information will be used for smart urban governance including decision making, as well as policy formulation and evaluation.

The pan-European innovation action develops innovative governance process deploying digital solutions to transform citizen’s engagement and cities’ effectiveness in delivering European Green Deal objectives for carbon neutral development. Green and digital transformation to carbon neutral cities is promoted via two interrelated project dimensions.

- Enhancement of intelligence applied to city decision making process and governance by engaging with citizen observations integrated with Copernicus, GEOS, in-situ and socio- economic intelligence, and delivered by innovative governance models based on novel toolboxes of decision-making methodologies and technologies.
- Harnessing the social and cultural opportunities to promote the active engagement of citizens via COs in the collection and use of urban decision-making intelligence support.

Figure 2: GREENGAGE vision – European Green Deal Areas

GREENGAGE exploits recent breakthroughs in smart city governance solutions providing an innovative opportunity to integrate new Copernicus derived intelligence with in-situ and socio-economic data. All this supports enhanced decision-making process, and delivery of essential integrated policy co-benefit solutions. The main driver of these transformations is the more readily available authoritative data and information on the urban environment, where citizens act as key enablers, as producers, consumers, curators, and owners. For this, innovative approaches to engage and empower citizens from diverse groups through an intersectional approach to research, are developed. In this respect, the concept of citizen-based environmental monitoring provides an effective opportunity to strengthen existing monitoring capacities increasing the urban data volume as well as enhancing the validation of data, trust in data and providing co-creation opportunities to inform evidence-based policy making.

The twin project objectives enhancing urban governance evidence-based decision-making, and promoting citizen engagement in that process have been developed, deployed, and fully demonstrated in 5 pilot engagements, in selected European cities and regions including: Bristol (the United Kingdom), Copenhagen (Denmark), Turano and Gerace (Italy) and the region of Noord Brabant (the Netherlands), see Figure 1 in summary section above.

Each of these innovation pilots' actions target specific EU Green Deal objectives: areas 1, 5, 8, 9 and 10. These actions aim to highlight the opportunity for smart city governance by promoting citizen engagement, co-creation, gathering new data which complements existing datasets and evidence-based decision and policy making.

The structure of the present report is as follows:

- Chapter 3 provides an overview of the nature of the urban planning and governance challenges faced by European cities today in the context of the climate change emergency as well as the impact of a post-Covid “new normal”. Both pose enormous challenges to existing models of urban governance and highlight the need and opportunity for Citizen Observatories to enhance engagement and more effective decision-making process and implementation. Deliverable D2.5 extends this analysis and conceptualises climate change governance as a wicked issue, defined fundamentally by the different normative views of stakeholders and the practical actions that emanate from these. This requires a form of governance that is comprehensive, inclusive and deliberative. This provides a rationale for the discussion of smart urban governance models that follows in the remaining chapters.
- Chapter 4 introduces initiatives promoted by recent EU funded research in developing a new urban governance of enhanced open bottom-up engagement in the formal processes of top-down urban planning. The section introduces the smarticipate urban governance model (Horizon 2020 2016–2019) as a conceptual frame for development of the GREENGAGE solutions, as well as the conceptual base for Citizen Observatories. Drawing on the framing of climate change governance as a wicked issue, Deliverable 2.5 builds on this framework and considers the potential of a “systems thinking” approach to governance – one that makes sense of climate change by considering the totality of the field of action and using it as a vehicle for integration, inclusion and deliberation.
- Chapter 5 offers an overview of recent published literature and EU project related information concerning the nature of smart urban governance, the associated models, and methodologies, as well as Citizen Observatories related research. Deliverable 2.5 extends the previous literature review, to explore more fully the potential and limitations of citizen science and Citizen Observatories as a means of delivering engagement and deliberation within a systems thinking approach to smart urban governance.
- Section 6 presents an analysis of the results of a Pan-European Survey. The survey was carried out to understand how other cities and organisations govern Citizen Observatories.
- Section 7 gives a brief specification of the aims and objectives, and methodologies of the 5 GREENGAGE innovation pilot actions.
- Section 8 outlines the initial specification of the GREENGAGE governance models for each of the 5 GREENGAGE innovation pilots.
- Finally, Section 9 addresses what activities and processes should be adopted to establish Citizen Observatories.

3 Green and Digital Transitions – Grand challenges

This chapter argues that the challenge of climate change adaptation and mitigation constitutes a “wicked” issue. It is a conundrum of singular complexity, defined fundamentally by contending stakeholder interpretations and (proposed) solutions. As such, a fundamental reform of urban governance is required; one that is *holistic* (necessitating an evidence-based understanding of the urban ecosystem, supported by comprehensive data collection), integrative (engaging multiple stakeholders in a cohesive system of multi-level governance), and inclusive (seeks to engage citizens effectively in these reformed structures and processes).

3.1 Urgency for New Solutions

The European Environment Agency report “Perspectives on Transitions to Sustainability” (EEA 2018) demonstrates that transitions in the societal systems that drive environmental degradation and climate change are essential if Europe is to meet its sustainability goals in coming decades. Europe's persistent sustainability challenges are systemic, in the sense that they are tied in complex ways to prevailing economic, technological and social systems. These interlinkages often make it hard to effect rapid reductions in socio-economic and environmental pressures. Nonetheless, it is necessary to go beyond incremental improvement to secure fundamental transitions or transformations in core systems, entailing profound changes in dominant institutions, practices, technologies, policies, lifestyles and thinking. These include the consumption-production systems that meet key human needs, including food, mobility and energy. The urgency of the tasks confronting urban planning are identified by the European Green Deal challenge to define decarbonization pathways for transition to “net-zero neighbourhoods” by 2030 (European Commission 2019). The pandemic has given rise to the notion of a “new-normal”, reflecting changes in attitudes and behaviours evident as Covid-19 propelled cities and citizens through a decade of digital transformation overnight (Budd and Ison 2020). Covid-19 now joins the climate emergency in highlighting the importance of resilience and adaptability in urban planning, whilst throwing into sharp relief the limitations of urban governance. As a consequence, urban planners across Europe are facing a common challenge to develop effective planning solutions for a deeply uncertain future, and influence the transformative capacity of cities to deliver on carbon neutrality, whilst transitioning towards the post-pandemic “new-normal”. Urban planners are responding to these challenges and actively working to understand how to envision the net-zero neighbourhood as hubs of living and working, and how to shape behavioural change strategies to respond to the new socio-economic and spatial realities of cities. Frequently visions deploy 15-minute city and liveable neighbourhood concepts of mixed urban land-use providing housing, employment, education, shopping, and cultural facilities within easy walking and cycling distance. These planning solutions target the delivery of “win-win” policy co-benefits associated with climate change mitigation options, including improved air quality, more healthy cities and citizens, living in socially cohesive and economically vital local communities.

3.2 Governance and Management

Today the new socio-economic realities of post-pandemic life define requirements for redefined decarbonization pathways to form fundamental components of urban planning. Critically, new visions are required to support the specification of the mitigation and transition pathways and associated strategies to deliver EU climate goals. Planning strategies based on decarbonisation pathways can then form central components of a new governance delivering effective transformation strategies in the urban context (Moberg et al 2019). Governance and the management of the socio-economic characteristics of the city is critical to the delivery of transitions to the net-zero neighbourhood. These characteristics are defined in a spatial and territorial context that determines the extent to which the cities of Europe positively contribute to Europe's global commitments to halt climate change by reducing greenhouse gas emissions and deliver a range of associated policy objectives. Here the extent of urban sprawl, the population density, and the dominant mode of transport between homes and work, and recreational and cultural facilities substantially determine the level of greenhouse gas emissions, air quality, energy efficiency, and the health of both society and the economy. Furthermore, the form of the city and its physical connectivity and interaction with its hinterland substantially determines the wider impact of the city on the natural environment, and the conservation or loss of biodiversity. Cities embody the twofold challenge currently facing the European Union, on the one hand how to improve competitiveness while at the same time achieving social cohesion and environmental sustainability. As any policy planned for a certain sector will end up affecting the others in one way or another, a good understanding of urban

dynamics, as a pre-condition for an integrated planning of transport, housing, work areas, public spaces and services, is key for a successful, sustainable urban development. Complex problems like these therefore require a holistic approach to urban development, together with an integrated assessment of urban policies supported by a comprehensive set of economic, social, and environmental sustainability indicators.

3.3 Integrated Governance

Urban governance and spatial planning has a special role in delivering Europe's global commitments as it underpins all other policy areas and is therefore the focus and epicentre of these integration requirements, specifying integrated spatial solutions, via a variety of policy instruments including both neighbourhood and strategic city-wide planning. City planning and governance integration targets the management of the interconnected socio-economic and environmental characteristics of the city region in a spatial framework. This demands the creation and deployment of intelligence generated by multiple agencies in a multi-layered framework of governance and applied to myriad of cross-thematic societal challenges seeking optimal solutions. The process continues via plan implementation according to a spatial vision that seeks to understand and realise the city of 30 years hence. Complex and interconnected facets of the urban ecosystem demand systemic and integrated assessment of spatial impacts in terms of socio-economic and environmental indicators to secure the essential "win-win" policy co-benefit that are central to the delivery of the transformation agenda adopted by politicians globally. Policy making directly or indirectly relevant to urban development connects vertically local, regional, and national authorities to supra-national political authorities, as well as horizontally across services concerning transport, energy, environment, land use, etc at the local city level. So there is a need for coordination at all levels of government and for an integrated and cross-sectoral approach, as well as cooperation and networking between cities, in order to ensure effective multi-level governance, coherent strategies and efficient spending of public resources. The central requirement for integrated approaches to sustainability transition has long been advocated as an essential response to socio-economic interdependencies and the multi-scalar nature of governance responses in a pan-European framework. Integrated, sustainable, cohesive, and inclusive urban development is the most effective way to achieve greater economic competitiveness, eco-efficiency, social cohesion, and civic progress in European cities, and to guarantee citizens' quality of life and welfare.

3.4 New Urban Governance

Central to the realisation of the "new normal" planning solutions is therefore an integrated urban planning methodology leveraging stakeholder co-design, generating climate strategy and action plans that are transformative and agile in respect of demands for carbon neutrality that are the focus of the transformation agenda (Sharifi 2021). However, the limitations of existing urban governance models are thoroughly exposed by the demands of integrated and transformative planning, emphasising the urgent need for new solutions. This is prompting the reconsideration and redefinition of design principles and operational rules for a "new urban governance" (Cruz, Rode and McQuarrie 2019). The current reality is that inadequate governance arises as a result of a number of factors including the growing mismatch between administrative delineations and the functional urban area that extend far beyond the boundaries of the municipality of the core city. In emerging large polycentric city-regions, urban structure is often composed of a network of small and medium, urban, peri-urban and rural municipalities located around the major urban centre. Urban policies must be defined at a larger scale than municipality scale for operational reasons in order to provide better services for users e.g., public transport, for cost-efficiency reasons in order to share costs e.g., utilities, infrastructure, public transport; for strategic reasons in order to develop policies at the appropriate scale, and involve the key actors e.g. economic strategies and programmes. In this fragmented environment both institutionally and spatially, urban governance is undermined by insufficient coordination and integration between the large number and the variety of actors, private and public, operating at different territorial levels e.g., municipalities, metropolitan area, and city-region, with various competences. One casualty of this fragmentation is a planning authorities' ability to monitor both the outputs and outcomes of the plan. The data that exists, is largely unavailable, inaccessible, and lacking in common standards or clear purpose, resulting in overproduction, a short shelf life and limited re-use of data by other departments or stakeholders (Future Cities 2017). As a consequence of the various challenges identified above transformational governance, which attempts to drive the socio-economic and environmental transformations necessary to deliver the sustainable development objectives adopted by all cities of Europe, is confronted with the limitations of the policy

instruments that are inadequate to deal with urban complexity. Furthermore, current governance models are insufficiently agile to cope with the entrepreneurial environment encountered, and to respond to the pace of change in demography, societal expectations, and technology etc.

3.5 Engaging Stakeholders

Accordingly for urban planning whilst integrated assessment is essential, it is nonetheless and insufficient requirement for the resolution of these challenges, and the delivery of the urban transitions demanded. The implementation of sustainable urban development by city planning also requires the full engagement of all stakeholders and the involvement of civil society, enhancing transparency, accountability and trust in governance and the decision-making process. Besides public and semi-public sectors, the policy-making process also involves heterogeneous actors from private sector, third sector and citizens. These private sector including firms and companies operate at national e.g., infrastructure providers, regional, city and individual e.g., property development companies. Third sector agencies including NGOs, civil society organisations, non-profit-making organisations e.g., interest groups, ecological associations, neighbourhood committees, are also engaged. For policy-makers and decisions-makers, dialogue with citizens is not only a way to understand society's expectations but also to identify barriers and opportunities for transformation, supporting the effective implementation of policies. At the same time innovation and broader societal engagement in systemic change is promoting demands for open and participatory styles of governance based on social interaction and information sharing. In response urban planning is transitioning from a centralised, top-down perspective, engaging with bottom-up solutions within top-down governance frameworks, to make governance process and decisions open, fostering stakeholder engagement and improving the quality of decision-making. ICT is a key enabler (EEA 2022) in making this possible supporting the development of tools and methodologies that address top-down integrated urban planning while simultaneously developing the interconnection of open governance service and the co-design of planning solutions.

3.6 Climate change governance as a “wicked issue”

It is helpful to describe climate change as a ‘wicked issue’ (Jordan 2010; Loorbach, 2010). That is, a complicated and insoluble challenge for which there is no straightforward remedy, due to rival stakeholder interpretations of the problem and the response to it (Weaver et al, 2023). It is not possible to envision solutions to a wicked issue that may be expressed as ‘right’ or ‘wrong’, merely more or less ‘good’ or ‘bad’. The policy response chosen will create its own set of (more or less ‘good’ or ‘bad’) consequences. Wicked issues are, therefore, never conclusively ‘solved’; they are merely re-solved repeatedly. As noted above, the existing governance infrastructure is poorly adapted to respond to a challenge of such complexity (van Zeiji-Rozema et al, 2007) as these do not align with the division of competencies within and between tiers of government.

Climate change has even been described as a “super wicked issue” (Levin et al, 2012). It is characterised by numerous further complications; the limitations of time, the lack of a central political authority, the tendency for policy makers to defer responses to the future; “super wicked problems are confounded by the tendency of our political institutions to make decisions that give greater weight to society’s immediate policy interests and to delay required behavioural changes, often by the use of ostensible commitments to reduce greenhouse gas emissions that have little or no immediate effect” (ibid.).

The term ‘wicked issue’ was introduced by US planning scholars Horst Rittel and Melvyn Webber (1973). They argue that all public policy challenges could be understood as ‘wicked issues’ because the rational-technocratic planning of the mid twentieth century (built on the scientific expertise, professional authority and public interest ethos of the public official, and definition of problems in accordance with explicit measures of efficiency) was increasingly inadequate to accommodate the needs and aspirations of a pluralist society. Rittel and Webber’s proposed response was an inclusive societal dialogue that recognised a greater plurality of perspectives than the rational-technocratic model. They, thus, anticipate many of the contemporary debates on the governance of climate change, considered below, by four decades (e.g. Frame and Brown, 2008).

Several related perspectives in the literature, referred to as ‘collaborative’ or ‘deliberative’ planning, have emerged as a new orthodoxy in opposition to the rational-technocratic model (Healey, 2005). Deliberative governance argues that, through free and open dialogue, social actors can achieve a shared

understanding of, and response to, a mutual challenge. It is assumed that not all stakeholder viewpoints are fixed and that these can evolve through reasoned argumentation. Deliberative perspectives posit the need for a consensus-oriented (Ansell and Gash, 2007) decision-making process based on deliberation; a process of evaluating rival claims through dialogue that is, according to (Fishkin and Luskin, 2005), informed (supported by factual evidence); balanced (contested by counter arguments); conscientious (conducted with decorum and respect); substantive (arguments are considered on their essential worthiness); and, comprehensive (all viewpoints are afforded due attention).

Urban planning literature has long recognized the shortcomings of a rational-comprehensive, top-down approach to urban space. By the mid-20th century, this conventional planning method faced growing criticism for overlooking the diverse needs of citizens and creating homogenized public spaces (Friedmann, 2010). Pioneering research by William H. Whyte (1980) and Jane Jacobs (1961), among others, underscored these limitations, highlighting the significance of everyday street and community life. Their work advocated for diversity, representation, and community-centered planning strategies. Similarly, across the Atlantic, Henri Lefebvre (1968) emphasized the social dimensions of urban spaces and introduced the concept of the “right to the city,” advocating for active citizen participation in urban governance. This call for inclusivity and meaningful engagement became a cornerstone of critiques against traditional urban planning models. They believed the classic urban planning models lead to and have the potential to exacerbate discrimination, power imbalances, and inequalities.

However, the rational-technocratic model of public policy has exhibited a certain resilience (Rydin, 2010). It is argued, for example, that the holistic ideal of sustainable development has been displaced as the new meta-narrative by the narrow goal of carbon control (While et al, 2010). This is, in principle, a more workable policy objective, that is amenable to technical and market-based actions. The scope of climate change policy has become more biased towards mitigation, focusing on measures to optimise energy production, distribution and consumption. Policy and practice have duly become dominated by producer interests, supply side considerations, and the development of more ‘sustainable’ products, at the expense of pursuing changes in social behaviour (Bulkeley and Castan Broto, 2012; Castan Broto and Bulkeley, 2012). Conversely, Farrell and Hooker (2013) argue science and engineering are no longer understood as rational-technocratic endeavours, but context sensitive processes that give rise to dynamic theories with which humans attempt to understand the world.

Nevertheless, as Lonngren and Svanstrom (2016) argue, the most pressing climate change issues are not purely technical ones. A fundamental dilemma of wicked issues is the discord between stakeholders, perpetuated by politics and vested interests. Research shows that deliberation and the role of community engagement is underscored as a critical component in the development of sustainable, climate neutral, future-proof cities (Bokolo, 2023). Voorberg et al.(2015) distinguishes three types which differ in their degree of citizen involvement in urban development: 1) citizen as a co-implementer, citizens participate in the implementation of public services, taking over specific tasks traditionally performed by public organizations; 2) citizen as co-designers, citizens are involved in designing the service delivery process, often in collaboration with public organizations; and, 3) citizens as initiators, citizens take the initiative to formulate and develop specific services, with public organizations acting as supporters or facilitators (Voorberg et al., 2015). The objective of community engagement is “social innovation”; the creation of long-lasting outcomes that aim to address societal needs by fundamentally changing the relationships, positions and rules between the involved stakeholders, through an open process of participation, exchange and collaboration with relevant stakeholders, including end-users. (Hartley 2005; Bason 2010; Osborne and Brown 2011; Sorensen and Torfing 2011; Chesbrough 2003, 2006).

A basic challenge is the transition from deliberation to action. Levin et al. (2012) argue that traditional governance approaches have prioritised over ambitious “big bang” type policies that provoke either resistance, or practical but “weak” policies that are not proportional to the challenge. The climate change risks from “business-as-usual” attitudes and the precarious delivery of radical approaches suggest that a focus on intermediate interventions is warranted. Levin et al (2012) argue for a ‘progressive incremental’ approach that explores how modest actions produce significant aggregate returns over time. The model is based on the idea of ‘path dependency’; policies that ‘bind our future selves’ through recognising and linking chains of events that could influence the future (ibid.). Timely actions set a system on a trajectory; future stakeholders are limited to certain options dictated by previous events. These actions must converge to 1) increase incremental support for the intervention and 2) augment populations that favour the intervention, to counter ‘lock in’ of unsustainable pathways; and 3) to embed more sustainable trajectories through reinforcing incremental support for (initially) small actions (ibid).

Weaver et al (2023) advocate a similar approach described as “soft transformative governance”. In line with these emerging perspectives, the GREENGAGE project adopts a pragmatic yet forward-looking stance by operationalising deliberative and soft-transformative governance models across its diverse pilot areas. These include both metropolitan and rural settings, such as the Italian municipalities of Turano and Gerace, which offer valuable insights into how small-scale, community-driven innovations can scale into broader systemic changes (see Deliverable D2.4 Smart Governance Models 1). The soft transformative model promotes governance structures that seek to maintain sensitive socioecological systems by accruing small scale changes. The ultimate objective is system-wide change by covertly using a marginal gains approach to temper apparently unmanageable wicked problems by making them progressively less wicked. Associated complexity, uncertainty and stakeholder dissonance is thereby greatly reduced, and the problem made amenable to systematic resolution (ibid.).

3.7 Summary

In this chapter, we have described climate change adaptation and mitigation as a “wicked issue”, reflecting its essential complexity and elusiveness. These qualities require a transformation of urban governance, to one that emphasises integration, inclusion and integration. In the following chapter, we examine this challenge further, exploring how a “systems thinking” approach to urban governance might help to realise these principles.

4 Towards a new urban governance

In this chapter, we explore potential new models of urban governance, commensurate to responding to the “wicked” challenge of climate change adaptation and mitigation. We revisit the “smarticipate” model advocated in Deliverable 2.4 (2023) and examine in greater detail the potential for a “systems thinking” informed approach. That is, one seeks to understand and approach the challenge by considering it in its totality, as a vehicle for a model of smart urban governance that is integrated, inclusive and deliberative.

4.1 Next generation governance – smart models

Knowledge creation, sharing and use are fundamental to the governance of sustainability transitions. Yet developing the knowledge needed to support transitions presents diverse challenges that also requires transformation of the existing knowledge system, including the creation of open governance structures that promote knowledge sharing across government and society more broadly, as well as the development of more forward-looking information. There is therefore a need for fundamental change in these systems, including urban, fiscal and financial systems, and knowledge systems supporting decision-making, within the governance model, all issues central to the focus of this report.

Municipal experts providing a top-down view of the urban vision, and its local level specification, are no longer able to manage the inherent complexity of the sustainable city alone. Greater bottom-up stakeholder engagement thereby enhances the quality of integrated assessment necessary to effectively plan the modern city. Moreover, all urban governance and spatial planning decision-making processes require the drive of political mandate for the urban plan secured from stakeholder engagement, generating the political will essential to implement the plan. In various ways stakeholders including citizens, business representatives and civil society organisations are increasingly engaged in the decision-making process to facilitate political decision-making, providing endorsement of plans and development proposals, all essential to secure the democratic legitimacy of the urban plan. In this way citizen science deployed via Citizen Observatories supports the enhancement of the quality of engagement rising from contribution to collaboration and finally co-creation (Figure 3).

To support this shift, it is crucial to adopt clearly defined methodologies linked to practical, accessible tools that enhance citizen participation and data-driven governance. Within the framework of Citizens Observatories, GREENGAGE promotes the use of a variety of instruments—such as air quality sensors, mobility tracking tools, and road condition monitoring through cameras and AI-based analytics. These tools not only help gather granular, real-time environmental and infrastructure data but also empower citizens to play an active role in shaping local policies.

In particular, the GREEN Engine represents a user-friendly collection of platforms and interfaces that encourages community-wide engagement by offering participatory features, access to open data, and feedback channels. Through this convergence of technological innovation and civic involvement, the GREEN Engine becomes a key enabler of collective intelligence. These methodologies and tools provide tangible leverage to collect meaningful input, foster transparency, and significantly strengthen the local governance capacity to address complex urban challenges.

Modified from Grossberndt, S., Liu, HY. (2016). Citizen Participation Approaches in Environmental Health. In: Pacyna, J., Pacyna, E. (eds) Environmental Determinants of Human Health. Molecular and Integrative Toxicology. Springer, Cham.

Figure 3: Citizens Observatories Enhancing Engagement

4.2 Generating Open Government Services

As urban governance has been changing towards a more dynamic and open architecture. Silo-based approaches are being replaced by cooperative governance systems and an unprecedented involvement of private parties managing solutions together with public entities is being encountered. Social, economic, and technological developments are leading towards the emergence of a new generation of open governance services. Such services are collaborative and digital based services characterised by a deliberate, declared, and purposeful effort to increase openness and collaboration through technology in order to deliver increased public value. These open, collaborative and co-production features exist in all phases of the design, deployment, implementation, and delivery of the services. More precisely the main features include:

- Openness: through the publication and accessibility of data, decision-making processes, and service components
- Collaboration: services recognising that government should not only aim at fulfilling societal and economic needs by direct service provision, but should enable and deliberately pursue collaboration of third parties;
- Technology: services fundamentally reliant on digital technology to deliver the services. Digital technology is used to provide disruptive innovation in the way services are delivered and is by definition collaborative, through open data, open web tools or collaborative platforms.

Next-generation governance and smart models build on technological progress that gives rise to new approaches to the management and the development of cities and the districts within them. Furthermore, growing urbanisation and the increased demand for efficiency in the provision of services is calling for more efficient urban management solutions. Smart Cities and the next generation

governance that they require therefore emerge as a strategy to tackle resource management and more generally, better manage cities' needs.

Smart city governance innovations are redefining the options and opportunities for city governance and urban planning globally. The interplay of societal and technological innovation provides a powerful dynamic that is driving the generation of new models of integrated and participatory, inclusive, and open governance. This dynamic has potentials to impact and disrupt the existing orthodoxies of governance and raises numerous questions for urban planning. What is the defining architecture of open, co-created and inclusive urban governance? What are the most effective transition pathways to this new urban governance? To what extent can common solutions and models of urban governance be applied universally, defining a new industry business model?

4.3 smarticipate: Open Integrated Governance Model

Many of these questions were addressed by the EU funded smarticipate project (Horizon 2020 Innovation Action, European Commission, 2016 – 2019) <http://www.smarticipate.eu/>. smarticipate - Smart Services for Calculated Impact Assessment in Open Governance engages with this transformational dynamic of cooperative governance systems to provide citizens with an opportunity to participate in the planning and decision-making processes. The smarticipate governance model accordingly is designed to be inclusive, collaborative, and data-driven, enabling citizens to play a more active role in shaping decisions and policy. The smarticipate governance model comprises 3 key elements (Figure 4):

- Integrated – demands for a more integrated governance arise from the challenges evident in the interconnected complexity of decision-making supporting the spatial planning of European cities. Effective decisions must be made in a 4-dimensional frame that aims to balance socio-economic and environmental considerations in the spatial framework of the city. Multi-sectoral governance requiring policy and practice coherence between the levels of governance, from local to global further compounds the integration challenge.
- Open and participatory – open participatory stakeholder engagement in the co-design, development and delivery of urban planning solutions provides an essential bottom-up dynamic and counterpoint to top-down expert, but often inadequate solutions. Open engagement with urban stakeholders deploys their potential as experts in their own communities, introducing the creativity of new and relevant solutions for intractable urban problems. Open governance also promotes the legitimacy of democratic engagement, building capacity for enhanced political will, driving implementation and transformation.
- Common - common global drivers of change including climate change, economic transition as well as demographic and migratory forces impact cities with remarkable similarity, wherever they are located. Political solutions to these societal challenges, defined in the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals and the EU Urban Agenda are designed on a global and regional stage, but delivered locally by cities acting collectively for common purpose. Essential communication between government decision making systems to secure policy coherence and collective implementation effectiveness, depend on the interoperability of common information systems that deliver this intelligence to decision-makers.

Figure 4: smarticipate Governance Model

4.4 A “systems thinking” approach to climate change governance

The complexity, uncertainty and contested nature of the challenge of climate change has often led to calls for an “holistic” or “systems” based mode of governance. Such an approach can be defined as one that seeks to encourage: “the ability to collectively analyse complex systems across different domains (society, environment, economy, etc.) and across different scales (local to global), thereby considering cascading effects, inertia, feedback loops and other systemic features related to sustainability issues and sustainability problem-solving frameworks” (Wiek, Withycombe and Redman 2011, p.207).

However, Porter and Cordoba (2009) argue that such an approach has often been imprecisely defined and applied. They identify three basic approaches to systems theory (see also Lonngren and Swanstrom, 2016):

- *Functionalist*. This perspective assumes that the “system” comprises the sum of its individual elements, each of which can be delineated and developed independently. The purpose of policy is to formulate the single most effective solution to the problem. The challenge of climate change is, therefore, primarily a scientific-technical one. The appropriate form of governance is one of top down, command-and-control managerialism. Functionalist approaches are most appropriate for problems that are clearly delineated.
- *Interpretive*. This frame of reference regards the system as greater than the sum of its parts and socially constructed rather than objectively defined. Definitions of problems are based on the normative beliefs of different stakeholders. The challenge of climate change is, therefore, not reducible to technical responses. Competing ideas must be openly debated in a democratic forum. The appropriate form of governance is, thus, deliberative, participatory and inclusive. Interpretive approaches assume that conflicts are ultimately resolvable.
- *Complex adaptive systems*. This viewpoint defines the system as characterised by self-organisation and bottom-up change. It is, by definition, uncertain and unmanageable in a top-down manner. The appropriate form of governance is, thus, one that recognises the impossibility of attaining perfect solutions, but facilitates the most advantageous choices given these constraints.

In practice, the application of systems thinking to decision making combines all three different methods, albeit in different contexts (Porter and Cordoba, 2009; Lonngren and Swanstrom, 2016).

Multi-scale policymaking involves developing, implementing, and evaluating policies at interconnected levels, acknowledging that decisions at one scale influence others. However, large-scale policies - such as those at the global or continental level - often overlook local contexts. Effective multi-scale policymaking can help address complex urban development challenges, such as climate change, by fostering alignment between different governance levels and encouraging flexible, collaborative

frameworks. In areas like public health, climate change, and urban development, coordinated efforts across governance levels are essential to ensuring that local actions contribute to broader regional, national, and global objectives. One of the primary challenges lies in managing the differing priorities and capacities of various governance structures. Solutions include fostering intergovernmental collaboration and designing adaptable policy frameworks that respond to local needs, with citizen science playing a crucial role in this process.

A good example of multi-scale policymaking in action is the New European Bauhaus (NEB) initiative^[1]. This EU-level policy integrates sustainability, aesthetics, and inclusivity into urban development while aligning local actions with broader policy goals. NEB addresses challenges in public health, climate change, and urban development by fostering intergovernmental collaboration and creating flexible frameworks that accommodate local contexts. A core element of NEB is its emphasis on citizen engagement at the grassroots level, ensuring that policies reflect the lived experiences and aspirations of local communities. This bottom-up approach helps bridge the gaps between different governance levels, making policymaking more inclusive and responsive. However, the initiative must navigate the complexities of diverse local contexts and manage potential conflicts among stakeholders to maximise its impact.

The impact of multi-scale policymaking is particularly evident in large infrastructure projects. In "Participatory Governance in Megaprojects: The Lyon–Turin High-Speed Railway Among Structure, Agency, and Democratic Participation," Esposito et al. (2023) examine participatory governance mechanisms in the Lyon–Turin high-speed railway project. Their study analyses two participatory venues—the Italian Observatory for the Turin–Lyon Railway and the French Public Inquiry—assessing their structural and agentic features and their influence on democratic participation. The findings indicate that both venues failed to enhance democratic engagement. The French Public Inquiry lacked the capacity to generate meaningful democratic value, while the Italian Observatory reinforced polarization between supporters and opponents of the development. The authors advocate for a deliberative democratic approach that prioritizes inclusive discourse and consequential decision-making, suggesting a shift from isolated participatory forums to a systemic model of governance. This systemic perspective views megaproject governance as a network of interdependent processes that require accountability from empowered actors and structured feedback mechanisms between public and decision-making spaces. The study ultimately calls for further research to systematically explore these governance dynamics and develop frameworks for democratizing decision-making in large-scale projects.

A comprehensive systems thinking approach must, therefore, consider the sociology and psychology of citizens and stakeholders involved in governance processes. Understanding human behavior and aligning it with policy decisions is crucial for developing inclusive and multi-scale governance models. Research from psychology, decision sciences, and systems sciences suggests that well-designed interventions can improve collective decision-making by making it more rigorous, transparent, and defensible (Rouvette & Franco, 2024). Additionally, incorporating a structural understanding within participatory processes can help influence behavior effectively.

Applying these principles across the citizen participation cycle underscores that citizens' responses to policy interventions mirror decisions made at higher governance levels. Governance models based on these principles may integrate top-down and bottom-up approaches, recognizing their interdependence and complementary roles. This aligns with the concept of polycentric governance systems (Carlisle & Gruby, 2019).

Human behavior also plays a vital role at the meta-level of governance models. People learn from these models and adapt their actions accordingly. A model representing causal chains—from interventions to system outcomes—can provide pathways (Bügelmayer-Blaschek et al., 2024) refined through participatory processes. Such iterative optimization can foster shared visions and lead to desirable outcomes. This approach is also referred to as backcasting, a concept introduced by Robinson (1982; 2003). Backcasting involves creating normative scenarios to explore how desired future outcomes can be achieved, contrasting forecasting, which focuses on projecting likely future scenarios. Backcasting asks, "How can we create a certain desirable future?" and "What actions are necessary and when?" rather than simply "What is possible?" This method doesn't always require a quantitative model but can be used in a participatory manner with simplified qualitative models to explore relationships and feedback loops. Systems thinking or system dynamics, when available, is especially suited for backcasting because it focuses on long-term system behavior and avoids the pitfalls of short-term optimizations. Rather than relying on a single action, backcasting emphasizes the interaction between

measures, maximizing synergy and preventing conflicts. This process can also help to transform reinforcing feedback loops with negative outcomes (vicious cycles) into positive ones (virtuous cycles), ultimately promoting positive social tipping points (Eker & Wilson, 2022). In effect, it represents a structured, goal oriented, form of the incrementalist approaches considered above.

How would a systems thinking informed approach to climate change work in practice? Figure 5 illustrates the multi-stakeholder collaboration required to address urban challenges, wherein a coordinated set of responses aligns with the Driver–Pressure–State–Impact–Response (DPSIR) framework (Smeets & Weterings, 1999). It is important to note that responses generate multiple causal pathways, creating a web of feedback loops. However, the complexity of such a model, considering diverse stakeholders, multiple governance levels, and various time scales, necessarily remains simplified in visualizations.

Figure 5. Systems thinking applied to city governance, using the DPSIR framework for simplified visualization.

A holistic approach is essential to address the various socio-economic, environmental, and political dimensions involved. Moreover, governance models must be reformed before meaningful changes in urban development policies can take place. Collaborative governance has long been recognized as a transformative approach in public policy and administration. By acknowledging the complexity of contemporary policy challenges, it fosters shared decision-making, collaborative problem-solving, and mutual accountability (Esposito et al., 2024). For co-creation to be truly effective, it must actively engage different stakeholders - particularly end-users (citizens) - at all three stages of space production and policymaking: formulation, implementation, and evaluation. Public engagement, therefore, empowers participants by enabling them to envision and act upon future changes. However, as Huttunen et al. (2022) note in their literature review, citizens rarely participate throughout the entire research process, and state organizations often fail to recognize the value of local knowledge. The extent of citizen involvement in different stages of policy formulation, implementation, and evaluation depends on several

factors, including the compatibility of public institutions with participatory governance, the attitudes of public officials, the presence of clear incentives, and the social capital of citizens (Voorberg et al., 2015).

The formulation, implementation, and evaluation of policies can benefit significantly from a systems thinking approach. This perspective allows policymakers to view governance as a complex and interrelated system, where decisions and outcomes are influenced by various actors, processes and connections between them, involving multiple feedback loops. Below, we elaborate on how these stages can be designed and managed using the principles derived from a systems thinking approach, as outlined above.

1. Policy Formulation

In the policy formulation phase, systems thinking encourages the consideration of all components and stakeholders involved in a given issue. Rather than focusing on isolated problems or linear cause-and-effect relationships, systems thinking emphasizes understanding the broader context, recognizing interdependencies, and identifying potential feedback loops that might arise as a result of policy decisions.

- **Broad Stakeholder Engagement:** Systems thinking stresses the importance of inclusive decision-making, where a wide range of stakeholders, including marginalized or underrepresented groups, are involved early in the process. This ensures that the policies are comprehensive, socially equitable, and grounded in the real needs of citizens. Using tools like public consultations, citizen advisory boards, and targeted communication efforts, marginalized voices can be included, thus ensuring policies are more inclusive.
- **Identifying Causal Relationships:** As part of the formulation phase, it's critical to map out the key drivers, pressures, and potential impacts that the policy aims to address. A Driver-Pressure-State-Impact-Response (DPSIR) framework (Smeets & Weterings, 1999) can be used to understand the system dynamics - how various factors interact and influence each other, and what unintended consequences may arise from potential interventions.
- **Cross-Scale Collaboration:** Policy formulation should also involve collaboration across various governance scales (local, regional, national) to develop solutions that are holistic and integrative. Information sharing across government levels ensures policies are aligned with broader goals, such as sustainability or social equity, and avoids conflicts or redundancies.
- **Backcasting Approach:** Systems thinking supports using backcasting as a planning method to ensure that policies are designed to achieve a desirable future, rather than merely projecting likely future scenarios (forecasting). By visualizing a long-term goal or outcome and identifying the necessary steps and actions to reach that goal ("pathways"), backcasting helps in formulating policies that are future-oriented and proactive. This also encourages thinking about where the most efficient leverage points are to address multiple problems with one policy, and how interventions at different levels of the system might work together to produce the desired outcomes.

2. Policy Implementation

In the implementation phase, systems thinking helps ensure that policies are executed effectively by considering the interconnectedness of different actors, sectors, and systems. It focuses on continuous learning and adaptive management, which are essential for responding to challenges as they arise and ensuring that the policy stays relevant over time.

- **Data and Information Flow:** The implementation phase requires a continuous flow of information across different stakeholders. A systems thinking approach ensures that data collected during implementation is shared across all relevant sectors and governance levels. For example, the integration of digital platforms (e.g., APIs, IoTs) can facilitate the exchange of data among various systems, enabling more informed decision-making. In GREENGAGE all mission data is stored in DRUID storage that enables different tools to access, analyse and visualise this data for different stakeholders. For instance, various dashboards can be developed for different stakeholders.
- **Collaborative Decision-Making:** Systems thinking emphasizes the need for participatory decision-making during the implementation phase. By involving citizens, stakeholders, and local actors, policies can be adjusted as needed in response to feedback. This can be done through

feedback loops, such as community forums, surveys, and real-time monitoring of outcomes. These feedback mechanisms allow policymakers to refine their approach and adapt to changing conditions on the ground.

- **Cross-Sector Coordination:** Implementing complex urban policies often requires collaboration across sectors, including government agencies, civil society, and private partners. For example, in the context of urban management or climate adaptation, various sectors (e.g., transportation, health, housing) must work together. Systems thinking ensures that these efforts are coordinated and that governance models support interoperability across systems and platforms, allowing data and decisions to be shared across boundaries.
- **Flexibility and Adaptation:** The systems approach stresses that governance is dynamic, requiring flexibility to respond to unforeseen issues or changes. Continuous monitoring, tracking, and evaluation should be part of the implementation process to identify challenges early and adjust policies accordingly. This might involve adjusting mechanisms based on collaborative monitoring (e.g., citizen-driven tracking systems) or engaging in real-time discussions about policy effectiveness and impact.

3. Policy Evaluation

In the evaluation phase, systems thinking plays a crucial role in assessing not just the outcomes of a policy but also the ongoing relationships between the various components of the system. Evaluation in a systems context focuses on a deeper understanding of both the direct and indirect consequences of policy actions, as well as on identification of feedback loops that may emerge.

- **Feedback Mechanisms for Learning:** A key principle is the establishment of regular feedback loops. Feedback from stakeholders (e.g., citizens, local government agencies, private sector) should be incorporated continuously. Evaluation is not a one-off process but a continuous cycle that allows for ongoing refinement and improvement of policies. This feedback might involve citizen feedback systems, public consultations, or open platforms where individuals can provide input on how policies are working on the ground.
- **Evaluating System Interactions:** Traditional evaluation methods may focus on isolated outcomes, but a systems perspective looks at how various components interact within the broader system. For instance, a policy aimed at reducing traffic congestion should not only be evaluated on its immediate impact on traffic flow but also on how it affects public health, air quality, and economic activity. Integrated evaluation frameworks (e.g., DPSIR) allow policymakers to assess the effectiveness of interventions in a holistic manner.
- **Adaptive Management and Iterative Optimization:** One of the key features of a systems-based evaluation is adaptive management, which emphasizes the need for continuous learning and optimization of policies over time. This process allows policymakers to identify feedback loops with negative outcomes (e.g., policies that unintentionally worsen a problem) and adjust interventions accordingly. Moreover, it can help transform vicious cycles into virtuous cycles, turning ineffective policies into more successful ones through iterative evaluation and adjustment.
- **Transparency and Accountability:** Evaluation processes must be transparent to ensure accountability and build trust in governance. Systems thinking encourages public involvement in the evaluation phase, allowing citizens to be active participants in assessing the effectiveness of policies. Independent oversight, public scrutiny, and strong accountability mechanisms should be integrated to ensure that the evaluation process is rigorous, fair, and transparent.

4.5 Summary

In this chapter we have explored a systems thinking approach that seeks to ensure that policy formulation, implementation, and evaluation are not considered as linear or separate stages but are interconnected and iterative. Insights and data from the evaluation phase feed back into the formulation process, helping to continuously refine policies over a longer time, allowing for adjustments based on real-time feedback. For example, during policy implementation, continuous citizen feedback (via surveys, participatory platforms, and advisory boards) can be used to inform adaptive policy adjustments. Simultaneously, evaluation through systems thinking ensures that both the intended and

unintended consequences of the policy are assessed in the context of the broader system, helping to optimize the policy through ongoing learning and feedback. By applying an approach based on systems thinking, policymakers are better equipped to design, implement, and evaluate policies that are both effective and resilient in addressing the complex, interconnected challenges of modern urban governance. In the following chapter, we consider the potential for citizen science and the specific form of Citizen Observatories to facilitate the “bottom up” dimension of a systems approach to smart urban governance.

AWAITING VALIDATION BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

5 Smart urban governance – literature review

The growing challenges faced by cities due to rapid urbanisation over the past decades has given birth to the term 'smart cities' (Leal Filho et al, 2016). To envision the goal of a smart city, smart governance holds significant importance (Leonidas and Christopher, 2016) and is a core of smart cities initiatives, without which the success and development of smart cities is not possible (Rodríguez-Bolívar, 2015). This is because sustainable cities require high quality planning and decision-making, and governance plays a central role in sustainable development (Leal Filho et al, 2016). As per European Parliament (2014), poor governance model is a barrier to successful implementation of smart cities.

Of multiple dimensions of smart governance, citizens' participation, transparency, participation, and collaboration are often attributed to good governance (Bingöl, 2022). Given the significance of citizens' participation, a number of projects have been initiated in the past. smarticipate is one of them. H2020 smarticipate project developed an online participatory platform. The objective of the project was to enable citizens and city administrations to establish a dialogue on new planning proposals or services. The objectives were met by (i) making use of Open Government Data; (ii) getting citizens opinion on the proposed planning initiatives by city administrations—promoting top-down participatory planning; and (iii) enabling citizens to co-create and share new innovative proposals with the community, thus promoting bottom-up planning and open innovation. smarticipate project provides an integrated top-down and bottom-up urban planning and decision-making approach to smart cities. In smarticipate, the openness of citizens' opinions and alternative proposal ratings provide a transparent and evidence-based approach to reflect citizens needs to influence planning decisions. SmartGov (2016-2019) developed support tools to link open data and social media into Fuzzy Cognitive Maps (FCMs); FCMs are modelling and visualising tools which facilitate policy-related discussions between citizens and governments.

A number of approaches, such as co-creation, collaboration, contribution, have been identified to facilitate citizens' participation. In recent years, Citizen Observatories (CO) has gained its significance for urban planning and policy making processes. CO are community-based environment monitoring and information systems that combine community monitoring with monitoring by policy-makers, scientists, and other stakeholders. CO enhance earth observation systems with citizen-generated observations. The term CO was first addressed in EU FP7 Topic ENV.2012.6.5-1: 'Developing community-based environmental monitoring and information systems using innovative and novel earth observation applications' (EC, 2014).

COs have been used in a number of projects including EU project CITI-SENSE (2012-2016) which developed Citizen Observatory to empower citizens to contribute to environment governance. The aim of this project was to facilitate citizens' participation in decision-making and co-operative planning. WeSenselt (2012–2016) developed a citizen-based observatory of water. WeSenselt employed both soft layers and hard layers. Hard layers comprised low-cost static and portable devices for sensing and transferring water related information to public authorities, whereas soft layers encompass use of collective intelligence of citizens for gathering information related to water. Based on the collected information, WeSenselt developed descriptive and predictive models and decision-making tools which integrated sensor and citizen-based data. Another important aspect of the project was to develop two-way feedback and environment knowledge exchange between citizen and public authorities for decision-making and governance. The governance model encouraged transparency, knowledge management, accountability, e-collaboration, and responsiveness. COBWEB (2012–2016) provided an opportunity to participate in environment governance to those who live within biosphere reserves. COBWEB integrated with INSPIRE and allowed fusion of citizen data and public authorities' data in order to support policy objectives.

H2020 also funded multiple Citizen Observatories projects including GROW (2016-2019), Ground Truth 2.0 (2016-2019), SCENT (2016-2019), LANDSENSE (2016-2020). GROW focused on creating sustainable citizen platform to generate, share, and utilise information on growing and the land. The project facilitated learning and testing of regenerative food growing techniques. Ground Truth 2.0 project delivered six CO with four in Europe and two in Africa. The observatories were related to spatial planning issues and land and natural resource management which includes water quality and quantity, air quality, phenology, biodiversity, heat, and human-wild life incidents. Citizen-based data collection was used for joint decision-making, cooperative planning, and environmental stewardship. SCENT facilitated citizen participation in environment policy making by equipping citizens to monitor land-cover use and changes

in their everyday lives by using the SCENT toolbox. LANDSENSE project developed CO for land use and land cover monitoring. The project extended GEOSS and Copernicus capacities.

Sisters' projects to GREENGAGE funded by Horizon Europe are Urban ReLeaf and CitiObs. Urban ReLeaf aims to co-create citizen-powered data ecosystems in order to support climate change adaptation, green infrastructure, and urban design planning. CitiObs supports Citizen Observatories to create, enhance, or scale up inclusive and diverse Citizen Observatories. The project aims to foster an active role of citizens in the observation of the urban environment using low-cost sensor technologies and wearables. The project's focus is on air quality and related environmental measures.

The current study shows that COs are already used for environment monitoring and data collection. However, the GREENGAGE aim is to promote innovate governance and assist public authorities to shape their climate policies by involving citizens to co-create and co-exploit green initiatives and develop COs. GREENGAGE will further investigate that how CO shape the governance model.

5.1 Citizen Science

As argued above, complexities within co-designed projects surrounding policy implementation and behavioral change, benefit from a systems thinking approach; in terms of providing a framework to enable better understanding of complex systems. This aids the navigation of non-linearities in urban governance, and interdependencies, dealing with multiple interrelationships, and helps tackle the changing dynamics that shape system behavior, from feedback loops to backcasting. We underline and invite the recognition of the importance of understanding behavioral responses in governance terms, so as to seek to align policy interventions with local as well as national, and indeed international, societal norms and expectations.

One of the persistent challenges in multi-scale policymaking is the tendency for global policies to overlook local contexts as they filter down to national and regional levels. Information overload and bureaucratic complexity often lead to citizen disengagement (Senabre Hidalgo et al., 2021). However, as argued above, active citizen participation in policymaking can help mitigate these challenges. While higher levels of governance provide overarching frameworks and resources, excessive centralization can limit local autonomy (Harvey, 2005). To counter this, inclusive, context-sensitive policies that empower local actors are essential. Participatory models enhance policy relevance and effectiveness, though codesigned approaches can be resource-intensive (Fung & Wright, 2003). Power dynamics must also be carefully considered, as deepening citizen engagement in research and policymaking strengthens democratic participation (Huttunen et al., 2022).

Barriers around accessibility and trust need to be priority considerations. To work toward improving inclusivity in city governance requires many other careful considerations, across spatial, social, economic, political, and environmental dimensions in urban settings. Proactively creating methods of inclusive public participation requires consideration of both existing participatory models as well as being open to experimental innovation. Social inclusion measures must form an integral part of city planning working practices; to be adopted ideologically as much as in practice with a holistic, organic approach, as well as a targeted manner at all stages of policy cycles. This includes up to the implementation stages, as well as when evaluating, through impact assessment. We argue below that citizen science projects not only empower volunteers but also enhance scientific literacy (Ballard et al., 2017). When citizen-generated data is integrated into policy decisions, multi-scale policymaking becomes more effective and responsive (Conrad & Hilchey, 2011). Consequently, codesigned citizen science fosters civic engagement and motivates continued participation (Irwin, 1995).

Citizen science is increasingly seen as an effective pathway for taming wicked problems through grassroots mobilisation and innovation (Hodgkinson et al, 2022; Weaver et al, 2023). In practice, citizen science involves the active participation of the public - often referred to as citizen scientists - in scientific research, encompassing data collection, generation, analysis, and interpretation. Beyond its scientific contributions, citizen science also offers significant advantages for policy evaluation. It fosters a sense of ownership and engagement among citizens, empowering them to assess policies that directly affect their lives (Esposito et al., 2024).

The past decade has witnessed a proliferation of citizen science activity. This had been led, in part, by advances in ICT. Digital transformation has significantly deepened the intersection of multi-scale policymaking and citizen science. Online platforms and mobile applications enable citizens to contribute to large-scale data collection, supporting global monitoring efforts (Silvertown, 2009). At the same time,

digital spaces provide marginalized populations with opportunities to voice their opinions and engage in scientific research (Haklay, 2013) and urban decision-making. These technologies also play a crucial role in disseminating scientific knowledge, fostering broader citizen engagement (Newman et al., 2012). For instance, local environmental monitoring projects generate data that inform regional and national policies, illustrating how digital tools might revolutionize multi-scale policymaking by facilitating communication, data sharing, and public participation (Dickinson et al., 2012). Scientists have also become more aware of the potential for citizen participation in the collection of scientific data, due to budget constraints (Liu and Kobemus, 2017). Moreover, a key limitation of established methods of environmental monitoring (e.g., Earth Observation through satellite data) is the restricted data and the disjuncture between these and citizens' everyday lives (Liu et al, 2014).

A subset of citizen science, codesigned citizen science has evolved over the past two decades (Bonney, 2007; Cohn, 2008) and actively involves community members in both the design and implementation of research (Bødker et al., 2022). This approach is particularly relevant for multi-scale policymaking in urban planning and technology development, where local knowledge can be integrated into broader policy frameworks. By contributing to real-world research, citizens witness tangible impacts from their participation. Codesigned citizen science serves as a bridge between different governance levels, incorporating diverse perspectives to create more responsive and adaptive policies. It also introduces explicit protocols for data collection, providing new opportunities for monitoring and advancing sustainability goals (Fraisl et al., 2020). Citizen science, this, has the potential to democratize both science and policy (Bonney et al., 2009) contributes to a more inclusive approach in urban development. Co-designed citizen science, especially in areas such as environmental and climate change research (Fraisl et al., 2020; Neset, 2021), enables community members to take an active role in designing and implementing research. When policies align more closely with the needs and aspirations of the communities they serve, they become more sustainable (Huttunen et al., 2022). Participatory processes not only generate a more accurate diagnosis of societal challenges but also help develop feasible and grounded solutions, thereby enhancing policy legitimacy by producing relevant data and addressing grassroots priorities.

Fostering a spirit of collaborative governance can further citizen empowerment, ensuring that diverse voices are integrated into decision-making. Citizen science serves as a powerful tool for public engagement, allowing people to contribute to scientific research and make science more inclusive and democratic. Through citizen science, individuals can explore the world around them and take part in meaningful discoveries, bridging the gap between professional researchers and the public while fostering shared knowledge (Wirtz & Muller, 2023).

In the context of inclusive urban development, citizen science opens new design opportunities that conventional urban planning struggles to address. While existing urban planning systems predominantly prioritize economic value (Adams & Tiesdell, 2010), bottom-up initiatives focus on broader social and environmental values often overlooked in formal policymaking. These inclusive urbanism approaches - also known as do-it-yourself urbanism (Iveson, 2013; Finn, 2014), temporary use (Colomb, 2012; Martin et al., 2019; Matoga, 2019), and self-organization (Boonstra & Boelens, 2011; Horelli et al., 2015; Partanen, 2015) - propose bottom-up urban developments as a form of citizen-led initiatives. These initiatives are often driven not only by citizens but also by independent professionals operating at the intersection of society and the market, achieving their goals through social entrepreneurship (Weerawardena & Mort, 2006; Certo & Miller, 2008), as discussed by Mens et al. (2021). These various models of alternative policymaking and citizen engagement are collectively encompassed within citizen science, which emphasizes co-creation among multiple stakeholders.

Liu et al, (2014) succinctly summarises the potential of citizen science as follows: “The Chinese proverb ‘Tell me and I’ll forget; show me and I may remember; involve me and I’ll understand’ is an apt quotation in this context, since both CS and COs have great potential to be a suitable instrument to raise awareness, increase citizen participation and support community-based environmental decision-making”.

5.2 Citizen Observatories

Research highlights the transformative potential of citizen science in policy making, where citizen involvement enhances both accountability and the generation of empirical evidence (Esposito et al., 2024). By integrating citizen science into policy processes, policymakers can co-produce knowledge with the public, improving the accuracy and relevance of policy assessments.

A key institutional mechanism for embedding citizen science in policymaking is the Citizen Observatory. These are “communities of citizens sharing tools and applications as well as community participatory governance methods that are aided by social media streams (Wehn et al. 2018).

A CO for supporting community-based environmental governance may be defined as “the participation of citizens in monitoring the quality of the environment they live in, with the help of one or more of the following: (1) mobile devices of everyday utility; (2) specialized static and/or portable environmental and/or wearable health sensors, and (3) personal, subjective and/or objective observations, information, annotation and exchange routes, coming from social media technologies or other similar platforms (Liu et al, 2014).

Citizen observatories function as governance bodies that formalize citizen participation, ensuring that engagement extends beyond data collection to actively shaping policy design, implementation, and evaluation. By establishing structured frameworks for monitoring policy effectiveness, facilitating deliberation, and institutionalizing bottom-up feedback loops, Citizen Observatories contribute to more democratic and informed decision-making processes.

Liu et al. (2014) summarise the key features of a Citizen Observatory as follows:

- **Two data layers;** the “hard” layer (e.g. physical sensor layer) includes static and portable devices for sensing and transferring environmental information via mobile devices, the “soft” layer (human layer) is harnessing citizens’ own observations of their surroundings/environment;
- **Top-down and bottom-up approaches.** The former are typically expert-led and often start with the formulation of visions of the future. The latter are taken by different public groups (citizens) who develop and try out new approaches to meet the challenges. The scientific knowledge and policy analysis (top-down) are combined with local knowledge, experiences and perceptions (bottom-up); and,
- **A two-way interactive communication model.** A shift from the traditional one-way communication model in which citizens are passive information receivers, into a two-way communication model, in which citizens become active stakeholders in information capturing, evaluation and communication.

Citizen Observatories (COs) serve as community-based environmental monitoring and information systems, allowing individuals to share observations through mobile phones and web platforms. These observatories empower citizens to participate in environmental management by collecting data, thereby strengthening earth observation systems with citizen-generated inputs. Digital technologies not only optimize data collection but also enhance collaboration between state and non-state actors, fostering cooperative efforts in sustainable development and urban management (Aichholzer et al., 2016; Gil-Garcia et al., 2015; Bolívar & Meijer, 2016; Chourabi et al., 2012).

A CO, therefore, includes observations from not just scientists and policy makers, but also citizens. An effective CO facilitates a two-way dialogue between citizens and other stakeholders, ideally resulting in fundamental changes to local environmental management, and, as such, social innovation (Liu and Kobernus, 2017). What differentiates Citizen Observatories from other citizen-science activity is the priority afforded to enabling governance and decision making, as well as the ultimate intention to bring change in society (ibid.).

The smarticipate model outlined above provides the essential governance framework for integrating GREENGAGE Citizen Observatories as a bottom-up dynamic into the existing governance model. The framework permits the positioning of citizen science in relation to the planning policy cycle of decision-making identifying the roles and responsibilities of all stakeholders in that decision-making process (Figure 6), and citizen science impact in deploying supplemental citizen science data in the policy debate and decision-making process, so adding value to the quality of the outcomes.

Figure 6: Citizens Observatories Driving the Policy Cycle

Citizen Observatories are community-driven initiatives that engage citizens in monitoring and reporting on environmental and urban issues providing a powerful tool for promoting citizen engagement in environmental management and decision-making, and for creating more sustainable and resilient communities. By involving citizens in the decision-making processes related to urban planning, observatories Citizen Observatories have the potential to make cities more sustainable and liveable for all.

Citizen Observatories - Key Dimensions

- **Participation:** aim to engage citizens in the data collection, analysis, and decision-making processes related to environmental and urban issues. This means that citizens are not simply passive recipients of information, but active participants in the Observatory.
- **Data:** rely on the collection and analysis of environmental and urban data, which can be obtained through a variety of sources such as sensors, mobile apps, and citizen science projects.
- **Collaboration:** often involve collaboration between citizens, researchers, and policymakers to co-create solutions to environmental and urban challenges.
- **Transparency:** emphasize transparency in the collection and use of data, as well as in the decision-making processes related to urban planning.

- **Accessibility:** aim to make data and information accessible to a wide range of stakeholders, including citizens, policymakers, and researchers.
- **Scalability:** should be scalable and replicable, meaning that they can be adapted to different contexts and locations.
- **Technology:** rely on technology such as sensors, data platforms, and mobile apps to collect, analyse, and share data.
- **Governance:** often require a governance structure to ensure that data is collected, analyzed, and used in an ethical and transparent way.

Citizen Observatories rely on the collection and analysis of data, emphasize citizen participation and collaboration, and aim to be transparent, accessible, scalable, and technology driven. Citizen Observatories typically involve the use of new technologies, such as mobile devices, sensors, and web-based platforms, that enable citizens to collect and share environmental data. The collected data is then processed and analysed using various techniques, including machine learning and artificial intelligence, to provide insights and actionable information for policymakers informing policy decisions and raising public awareness about environmental issues.

In practice, there is a paucity of research on the nature, scope and impact of Citizen Observatories. A systematic review by Rathnayake et al (2020) offered the following observations. Reliable and objective overviews of Citizen Observatories and their impact are limited. There are few case studies that demonstrate where such projects have had a discernible impact on environmental outcomes and decision-making. The primary substantive focus of extant COs has been the evaluation of air and water quality and, geographically, this activity was located primarily in the Global North, with only 7% of these Citizen Observatories or science studies focused on countries in the global South (ibid.).

Citizen engagement is considered a major driver of citizen-science initiatives for environmental monitoring, and ideals such as citizen empowerment and participatory democracy are used to justify citizen-observatory studies. The CO studies cited by Rathnayake et al (2020) used online campaigns, newsletters, posters, and other media accessible to the relevant community to attract citizens mostly engaged as volunteers who gathered data through technological instruments. However, and crucially, it was evident that the motivation to adopt a Citizen Observatory was not confined to, or indeed led by, citizen empowerment. The key motivation for most of the projects was the potential to extend the breadth and depth of data available. Most citizen-observatories tend to focus on testing the citizen-science approach as an affordable method of acquiring a large volume of environmental data. The literature reveals that one of the motivations to adopt a citizen-science approach is the lower costs involved in gathering data (ibid.).

For COs to be sustainable, community engagement must be maintained over time. The methods cited above generated a sufficient number of public users interested in knowing about the project but not enough to create a self-sustaining community of users willing to take part over an extended period (Rathnayake et al, 2020). Most of the studies reported higher volunteer participation in the initial stages, which progressively declined over time. Liu et al (2017) argue that active partnership building and publicity are essential over the long term. It is imperative to promote continually the CO platform and tools, to raise awareness, recruit, and sustain citizens' participation; "The old adage, "if you build it, they will come", does not apply" (ibid.). Engaging with volunteers to participate in any form of activity related to CS or COs is a formidable challenge. The people are reluctant to invest spare time and resources without return. It is, therefore, very helpful to engage and to retain citizens by clearly emphasizing the benefits of their participation, for example, improved health, knowing which areas are polluted, how to avoid exposure, and personal recognition (ibid.).

Ensuring data that is accurate is critical for maintaining the integrity of citizen science research and the policies that emanate from it. Robust validation processes are necessary to maintain data reliability and uphold trust in citizen-generated evidence (Conrad & Hilchey, 2011). What emerged clearly from the literature is that the quality of data plays a crucial role in making citizen-science approaches acceptable. CS approaches and COs require strict data management. The obtained data often contain errors and bias. However, special attention must be paid to accuracy and uncertainty, especially when comparing crowdsourced with referenced data.

Despite their undoubted potential, research indicates that COs often struggle to exert meaningful influence over policy making. While digital tools can enhance citizen participation, power does not

automatically transfer to the public simply by granting access to technology (Liu and Kobernus, 2017). Political control frequently limits their autonomy, as power imbalances between experts and political authorities constrain their ability to produce independent evidence. Findings are often framed to conform to pre-existing political objectives rather than open scientific inquiry, raising concerns about transparency and credibility. Consequently, COs risk becoming symbolic rather than substantive tools for democratic participation, undermining their intended role in policymaking. Citizens participating in environmental governance are considered a risk rather than an asset to decision-makers, since they might be in opposition to the plans of the authorities. The long-standing conundrum of citizen empowerment, addressing the fundamental imbalance of power, is not addressed, to ensure that the communities' opinions, thoughts, questions, etc., are not only heard, but are valued (ibid). Data exchange is much more than just providing data to users, and it transcends the sharing of ideas or questions. The key is that the user is encouraged to provide data inputs regularly and finds value in the way that this information is used. However, while this results in more data being generated it does not necessarily engage the users, who might be entirely passive data providers (ibid.).

While COs play a critical role in citizen empowerment, complex instructions and information can hinder effective participation. This highlights the importance of user-friendly interfaces and clear guidance, which can significantly improve user experience and encourage wider engagement. For example, the European Union's CITI-SENSE project enables citizens to monitor air quality, influencing environmental policies through community-generated data (CITI-SENSE, 2016). Similarly, the WeSenseIt project involves citizens in water management, improving resource allocation and strengthening public trust in governmental processes (Wehn et al., 2015). Additionally, COs contribute to education and capacity building, helping citizens understand and address local environmental challenges. For instance, the Ground Truth 2.0 project emphasizes co-creating knowledge with citizens, enhancing their ability to contribute to environmental monitoring and decision-making.

COs also have the potential to promote social inclusion by engaging marginalized communities in policymaking processes. Strategies for mitigating community disempowerment within multi-scale policy frameworks include adopting inclusive policy designs, strengthening capacity-building initiatives, and establishing mechanisms for holding higher levels of government accountable. Local governance plays a crucial role in addressing these challenges by empowering communities and ensuring more equitable policy outcomes. However, challenges persist, particularly the digital divide, which limits access to digital tools, data, and information for disadvantaged groups.

The literature highlights the complexity of urban governance in the context of COs, emphasizing several critical components for fostering an inclusive governance model:

- **Inclusive Stakeholder Engagement:** ensuring broad participation from marginalized and underrepresented groups through targeted communication strategies (Klößner, 2015; Markvica et al., 2020).
- **Engagement Across Policy Phases:** expanding stakeholder involvement throughout the policy cycle, from collaborative monitoring and behavior tracking to influencing decisions, policy evaluations, and co-creation (Ostrom, 1990).
- **Feedback Loops:** creating regular citizen feedback mechanisms that promote continuous learning and adaptation, incorporating insights and best practices, and adjusting governance structures as needed (Gigler and Bailur, 2014).
- **Collaboration Across Scales:** encouraging collaboration among different levels of government and non-state actors and fostering coordination across sectors to address interconnected urban challenges. A systems approach can help maximize co-benefits and synergies, and manage inevitable trade-offs (Bai et al., 2016; Oliveira et al., 2015).
- **Participatory Decision-Making:** striking the right balance between top-down and bottom-up decision-making, utilizing tools such as citizen advisory boards and public consultations, and shaping urban development decision-making and outcomes in their social, economic and environmental domains (Baud et al., 2021).
- **Data Ownership and Access:** defining clear data ownership rights, ensuring controlled access for relevant stakeholders, and implementing robust data governance to address concerns over privacy, security, and misuse.

- Capacity Building: providing training to citizens on data collection, analysis, and awareness-raising techniques.
- Transparency and Accountability: ensuring transparency in CO operations through public scrutiny, independent oversight, and strong accountability mechanisms.

5.3 Summary

In this chapter, we have explored, via a comprehensive review of the literature, the potential for citizen science and, specifically, Citizen Observatories, to provide a platform for an inclusive form of smart urban governance; the “bottom up” dimension of a systems thinking informed approach. We have noted the considerable potential for the engagement of citizen scientists to enhance the quality of decision through their contribution to data gathering and analysis, plus the potential for citizen empowerment that this engagement promises. However, we have also noted the formidable challenges to achieving the high ideals of citizen science, not least the residual imbalance of power between policy makers and the public, and also the investment of time and resource required to sustain citizen interest and participation. In the following chapters, we focus on how European cities and, especially, the GREENGAGE Pilots and how they have sought to realise an integrated, inclusive and deliberative approach to smart urban governance.

6 Results of Pan-European Survey

In parallel to the literature review described in previous chapters, a dedicated survey was set up in order to receive inputs from a broader range of stakeholders and of cities / regions across Europe, beyond the pilot regions involved in GREENGAGE as pilots. Although the achieved participation in this survey was not sufficient to present any statistical evaluation of results, the scope of this survey and a brief qualitative analysis of results (observed trends) is documented in this chapter.

6.1 Purpose and scope of the survey

The goal of this survey was to obtain inputs from a variety of European cities on opinions and experiences related to citizen participation, Citizen Observatories and smart governance processes. The completion of this survey should take between 10 and 30 minutes, depending on the amount of text inputs participants would like to provide.

The survey was completely anonymous; it was set up using the platform EUSurvey using Anonymous survey mode – refer to <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/greengage>.

Following target groups were addressed (respondents had to select one of these)

- Municipality
- Private sector partner
- NGO
- Citizen / representing group of citizens
- Researcher
- Other (to be specified)

Regarding the target cities and regions, following communities and distribution lists (amongst others) have been addressed (either directly or via official contact points):

- GREENGAGE Pilots
- Smarticipate cities and (9 European and 2 non-European cities)
- EU Mission Cities (100 cities in the EU and 12 cities in countries associated to Horizon Europe)¹
 - Contacted via e-mail RTD-HORIZON-EUROPE-MISSION-CITIES@ec.europa.eu
- Contact lists compiled for previous research projects
 - Above 30 additional cities, organisations and networks contacted.

The survey was structured into following blocks, each of them containing 4 – 6 questions:

1. General Background / contextual data: Gathering basic information about target group (role), main area of activity or interest, level of familiarity, size and name of city or region.
2. Citizen Participation: How are citizens currently involved in decision-making processes, main barriers to citizen participation, what tools or methods have been most effective, improvement of local governance outcomes by citizen participation.
3. Citizen Observatories: Own involvement in COs and experience, potential benefits of COs, experienced challenges or risks, in which areas could COs provide the most value for the city.
4. (Smart) Governance Processes: Understanding and examples of smart governance, important links between smart governance and Citizen Observatories, progress toward adopting smart governance practices, support tools for governance processes, relationship between smart governance and traditional decision-making processes / pure “top-down” governance models, use of outcomes of COs.

¹ refer to [Climate-neutral and smart cities - European Commission](#)

- Future Perspectives and Final remarks: most significant opportunity for improving citizen participation, support needed, successful examples from other cities, most important objectives for Citizen Observatories or smart governance initiatives.

6.2 Results and Conclusions

The following diagrams show some trends of the received answers. These results should be considered with reservation, however, due to the small number of answers (only 13).

Role:

Main area of activity (or interest):

City (region size):

Figure 7: Survey participants information: Role, area of activity and city size

How are citizens currently involved in decision-making processes in your city?

What do you think are the main barriers to citizen participation in your city?

Figure 8: Questions on citizen participation: Involvement and barriers

What tools (including ICT) or methods have been most effective for increasing citizen participation?

Figure 9: Questions on citizen participation: Most effective tools

Figure 10: Questions on COs: Benefits and challenges or risks

In which areas could citizen observatories provide the most value in your city?

Figure 11: Questions on COs: Areas where COs could provide the most value

Figure 7 presents the spectrum of roles, areas of activity and city size of the survey participants, while Figure 8- Figure 11 present the trends of answers for selected questions regarding Citizen Participation and Citizen Observatories.

From the results shown here and the text inputs received, we could draw a few conclusions – on purely qualitative level:

- Naturally, the survey had more respondents who are primarily researchers, all of them working in medium to very large cities. Municipalities were extremely hard to reach.
- "Traditional" forms of participation continue to dominate (e.g. public consultations, campaigns, workshops, citizen assemblies, etc.)
- The main barriers for participation are public awareness, short term political thinking and lack of trust.
- Respondents recognise the potential for ICT to facilitate participation (note, however, the bias caused by the large share of researchers)
- Obstacles for COs include data quality concerns, digital divide, political will, while data privacy concerns are not recognised as a huge challenge.

- Open data frameworks and good communication with citizens are seen as critical enablers for COs and their effectiveness in the context of smart governance processes.

AWAITING VALIDATION BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

7 GREENGAGE Innovation Pilots' - Specifications

In this chapter, we revisit the specifications of each of the five GREENGAGE Pilot areas, as outlined in Deliverable 2.4 (2023). These provide a background to each locality, summary of the aims and objectives of each local intervention, and the specific role of GREENGAGE Citizen Observatories in each case.

7.1 Pilot Specification – Bristol, United Kingdom

The East Bristol Liveable Neighbourhood (EBLN) is an existing initiative in Bristol, UK. It is in the inner East of Bristol with geographical coverage 1.7 sq KM. It has approximately 6,000 properties and businesses within the area. The City of Bristol has stated the ambition of becoming Carbon Neutral by 2030.

Liveable Neighbourhoods are areas of a city where improvements are designed in partnership with local communities to achieve a better balance between how streets are used for vehicles and people.

In June 2021 Bristol's Citizens' Assembly called for our neighbourhoods to be reimagined so that they are people-centred and more 'liveable', meaning they are safe, healthy, inclusive, and attractive places where everyone can breathe clean air, have access to better quality green and public space, and feel a part of a community.

Rolling out two Liveable Neighbourhood pilot projects were Mayoral priorities under the previous governance structure, and continue to be for the current Committee system, in place since 2024. For Bristol, with the East Bristol Liveable Neighbourhood (EBLN) being the first scheme to be piloted in the city. A strategic walking and cycling route, the Wesley Way, in east Bristol was identified along Beaufort Road through St George, Redfield and Barton Hill (Bristol/South Gloucester Route 3) in the Local Cycling and Walking Infrastructure Plan (LCWIP).

The West of England Combined Authority (WECA) has provided funding to use an area-wide approach to develop a Low Traffic Neighbourhood (Liveable Neighbourhood), rather than just design linear infrastructure for route improvements. The project area covers parts of five wards of Bristol: Lawrence Hill, Easton, St George West, St George Central and St George Troopers Hill, south of Church Road and north of the River Avon.

Liveable Neighbourhoods have been controversial in some areas of the country where they have been introduced rapidly. Therefore, it is vital for this project to be community led, with meaningful engagement at every stage in the process.

Keeping the above points in mind, the EBLN scheme is being implemented in various stages by the Bristol City Council. These include:

6. **Co-Discover:** In this phase intelligence gathering was conducted to determine the demand for a liveable neighbourhood within citizens in the area.
7. **Co-Design:** In this phase the Bristol City Council engaged with the citizens via meetings and street events to develop plans for a trial scheme.
8. **Trial scheme:** This is the next phase of the project currently underway. Temporary measures have now been implemented to redirect the flow of traffic through the pilot area to promote active travel and improve public transport reliability. The installation of temporary measures was expected to finish by the end of January. However, heavy resistance by some residents has caused significant delays in the progress of the trial phase.

The objectives of Liveable Neighbourhood programme are to:

- Improve local and citywide air quality and contribute to meeting the climate and ecological emergency.
- Improve residents' physical and mental health and wellbeing.
- Improve levels of physical and perceived safety in our communities.
- Contribute to reducing inequality and opening opportunities for all in our communities.
- Improve local accessibility and connectivity to shops, schools, services, and other amenities for everyone to move around safely and sustainably.

- Transform our neighbourhoods to places where people want to spend time, can interact with neighbours, and enjoy their unique identities.
- Reflect the needs and characteristics of the local community and increase the sense of pride and belonging.

The EBLN pilot project has utilised a co-design approach seeking feedback and input from the local community to help design a re-imagined streetscape that realises the vision set through the Citizen Assembly.

The first round of engagement, "Co-Discover" sought to understand what people loved about where they lived, and what they would like to change to make it even better. The community were invited to map the issues and opportunities through both in person and online events. The results of the Co-Discover phase of engagement are summarised [here](#).

The results of the Co-Discover phase helped set the priorities of the community and enabled the team to create several design tools that could help provide solutions to the issues raised. A [design toolkit](#) was published in advance of the second round of engagement, "Co-Develop".

The Co-Develop phase of engagement sought to understand and map, where and what measures, the community would like to see on their streets. Interactive workshops were hosted in person and online, where the design team would provide support and technical advice on what people would like to see on their streets. Innovative [engagement tools](#) developed by the Alan Turing Institute were used during the workshops to help the community develop a holistic design for the transport measures required to deliver quieter streets.

The outputs from the Co-Develop phase have been used to inform the development of a holistic scheme that addresses the needs of the community. The results of the Co-Develop phase of engagement are summarised [here](#).

This scheme will be implemented on a trial basis to understand how the scheme works, whether it achieves the aims and what improvements may be required.

The pilot now seeks to implement and monitor the phase 1 scheme as a trial, following the submission of an Outline Business Case to the funding body, WECA. This is being delivered using temporary materials and will remain in place for 6 months whilst further engagement is undertaken with the community to determine how the scheme could look if made permanent. The phase 2 scheme will deliver elements of the project that can only be constructed in a permanent way such as, new crossings and junction upgrades.

The pilot project will collect data throughout the trial scheme to determine whether the scheme is a success. GREENGAGE technologies will be deployed with citizen scientists to fill the 'data gap' that is often experienced with transport schemes. By directly involving the community in the data collection, monitoring and evaluation of the trial, the pilot project can build community trust with the Council and create greater transparency for decision making on how the scheme could become permanent.

The pilot project involves a multidisciplinary team of experts, including data scientists, software developers, transportation planners, and community engagement specialists, to ensure a participatory and user-centred approach. The pilot will also provide tools to citizens to define other experiments and make use of pilot and auxiliary open data to understand and solve problems deemed more relevant to the pilot community. These insights can provide useful insights to public administration for interventions and/or policy making.

The pilot project will be evaluated based on its ability to collect high-quality and representative data, generate useful insights and recommendations, and engage citizens in the project. GREENGAGE will play an important role during the current trial phase for monitoring and to provide useful insights based on which permanent interventions can be applied in phase 2 of the EBLN project. It is expected that during the trial phase two GREENGAGE Observatories (GOs) will be implemented that will provide an opportunity for GREENGAGE to help monitor the scheme and collect evidence for further decision-making.

7.2 Pilot Specification – Noord Brabant, The Netherlands

The Province of North Brabant is in the South of the Netherlands with geographical coverage 5,081km² housing about 2.5 million citizens. Due to its job and education opportunities, and appealing natural environment, the province is rapidly growing, which comes with challenges. Chief amongst which is a rapid urbanisation, creating a demand for 12.000 dwellings in liveable and sustainable neighbourhoods per year. To tackle this and associated traffic safety, health, inclusivity, economic and energy challenges the province of North Brabant envisions a transition to sustainable traffic and transport as a key pursuit (Provincie Noord-Brabant *et al.*, 2022). The policy aims at 20% more cycled kilometres by 2027 and 40% by 2040, achieved through stimulation of biking, but primarily through the provision of more space to use the bike in everyday movements, recreation, commute, and multimodal traffic.

Although the province already has a strong urban and even regional bike infrastructure (bicycle highways), the choice to shift to sustainable transport requires more than physical means. Some regional movements are too long for bike travel, so motorized vehicular travel plays a dominant role in the mobility of Brabant as well, with about 80% of the trips longer than 6km made by car (Provincie Noord-Brabant, 2020). The shift to sustainable transport has not occurred to its full capacity.

The goal of this pilot project is to generate knowledge on how to achieve a higher shift to sustainable transport, and that requires understanding why the car is still the most chosen modality, and what elements of the choice for bike travel can be strengthened to increase the appeal of that option. For this, citizens need to be engaged in the reflection on their choices as well as their travel patterns, and in the targeted identification of obstacles to the use of the bike. Having a better idea of how and why people choose to travel a certain distance with by bike or by car or other modes allows for the co-creation of optimal conditions for sustainable travel for as many people as possible in neighbourhoods and regional connections. Specifically, exploring means in which citizens can partake in the discussions around bike stimulation, based on their own experiences, is something the Province wants to explore.

The experiences and decisions of the citizens offer qualitative data on possible apprehensions to switching from car to sustainable transport. Involving citizens in the gathering and signification of this data can strengthen the policy agenda through a more grounded understanding of obstacles to sustainable travel, and the decision process that precedes it. Especially as a foil to the top down and data-driven process bike planning policy making, the experience of the biker is a valuable asset in making the network more useable. While focusing on giving more space to bike travel, this engagement can ultimately reflect on the liveability and sustainability of North Brabant.

The goal of this pilot project is to generate knowledge on how to achieve a higher shift to sustainable transport, specifically from car to bike, on smaller travelable distances. To increase that understanding, this pilot will collect and analyse different types of qualitative and quantitative data through Citizen Observatories. The specific objectives of the pilot project are:

- 1) To establish Citizen Observatories that can collect, validate, and interpret qualitative and quantitative data, and are structurally integrated into a dialogical approach to governance discussing the liveability and sustainability of Brabant;
- 2) The collection and validation of a range of quantitative data (e.g. maintenance scores and obstacle overviews) and qualitative data (e.g. the process of decision making in modality choices) by citizens through a variety of data gathering methods and the analysis of this data within a digital twin to assess discrepancies between provincial or municipal planning considerations and the lived reality of bikeability;
- 3) To include women and historically marginalized groups such as ethnic minorities, and disadvantaged populations in the gathering and signification to ensure an inclusive perspective on the assessment of liveability and sustainability;
- 4) To aggregate the mobility data into a digital twin to strengthen its use as an evidence-based decision support tool;
- 5) To experiment with a 3-layer approach within the digital twin to facilitate policy making, looking at the combination of macro (e.g., GPS, Satellite, land use data), meso (e.g., mobility and spatial data from transport companies, traffic organisations, and policy indicators), and micro (citizen gathered data on, for instance, mobility routes or decision processes) data;

- 6) To generate additional knowledge on the process of involving citizen gathered data and their subjective appraisals in the top down process of policy making. The goal is to involve citizens more intensely in governance through co-creation, while ensuring data-driven checks and balances;
- 7) To use the data and citizen engagement to improve the conditions for sustainable transport on, for instance, spatial, environmental, and community level;
- 8) To set up more targeted campaigns to remove obstacles for biking in the decision process.
- 9) The pilot project targets the mobility transition throughout the whole province. A possible starting point was the topic of maintenance. This was highlighted by the largest volunteer cycling organisation as the main topic that should be assessed by citizens, in contrast to policy maker planning. This meant identifying strategies for maintenance assessment, different experience categories, and possibilities of co-creation.

The pilot builds on earlier GPS data gathering schemes that included citizen actions by contacting different citizen panels, such as the SmartwayZ reizigerspanel or the OV-Reizigersoverleg, funded by but independent from the province. Through this previous researchers, initial qualitative categories are identified that serve as obstacles for biking, including also those experienced by non-bikers. The pilot will set up Cycling Labs to explore the obstacles and motivators in detail. Through planned workshops, the weight of different factors are discussed, and actionable points are drafted. The weather for instance is not something that can be controlled, but physical obstacles may be easier dealt with. Each session of the Cycling Lab dives into a specific biking behaviour that is currently deemed less appealing (e.g. commuting, cycling to shops, recreational biking), in order to identify obstacles and ways to surmount these. The cycling lab gathers survey data that will inform province wide data gathering campaigns surrounding a topic that can be addressed to remove obstacles to specific biking functions. The Province wide data campaign, informed by the Cycling Labs, was shaped together with the Fietzersbond – the largest volunteer biking organisation in the Netherlands. A survey amongst their members highlighted bike path maintenance as key topic that volunteers should gather data on to complement official measurement. Maintenance was also a topic suggested in the Cycling Labs as one of the key obstacles. The Citizen Observatory will engage citizens, with the help of the Fietzersbond, to cycle over bike paths throughout the province and in the municipality of Heusden that have been assessed by Provincial or municipal officials. The experience will be captured through a variety of digital and non-digital methods, such as a possible mobile app, to gather qualitative and quantitative data such as photos of maintenance characteristics, the paths cycled on, and their affective appraisal through surveys. This bottom-up micro data will be added by the pilot partners into a digital twin, capable of visualising the gathered data and combining it with other datasets. During the project the digital twin will also be further equipped with mobility data and a set of specific indicators that can be used to evaluate policy goals and possible macro data in the form of satellite or census data. The aggregation of these different layers can contextualise the (non-)biking behaviour of the Citizen Observatory, highlight salient correlations, and identify conflicting data sets or insights between Observatory data and Provincial databases

The pilot project is supported with the Argaleo DigiTwin a data aggregation and visualisation tool that can be used to support governance decision making. This digital tool already contains detailed data shared by municipalities (such as traffic, and traffic light data) and transporters (such as bus performances), the micro data of routing and citizen preferences gathered by the Citizen Observatories can be combined and visualised. The data will be analysed and visualized to generate insights and recommendations for facilitating the transition to bike use on regional and urban routes, as well as its associated neighbourhood improvements, to make them more liveable and sustainable.

These discussions will involve the Citizen Observatories into areas of governance, thus requiring a multidisciplinary team of experts, including data scientists, software developers, transportation planners, and community engagement specialists, to ensure a participatory and user-centred approach. Together with these groups, the province can assess focal points for campaigns to improve biking, either through advertising, spatial interventions, or stakeholder involvement such as employers. By including the citizen in the exploration of the topic and giving insight into the breaking points for their decision, the pilot introduces citizens to the data driven decision making process and involves them in a more bidirectional governance in order to solve problems deemed more relevant to the pilot community. These insights can provide useful insights to public administration for interventions and/or policy making. Simultaneously, exploring different ways in which citizens can contribute to this process as the actual

users of bike paths, is a topic of focus as well. The Province strives for a more inclusive form of policy making, and Citizen Observatories are a relevant case to experiment with.

7.3 Pilot Specification – Amager Vest, Copenhagen, Denmark

Amager Vest is selected as pilot demonstration site. It is the largest of districts in Copenhagen with 83.000 residents. It is located to the southwest of the city centre on the island of Amager, along the nature reserve of the 'Common'. It is a mix residential, commercial, and university (Law, Humanities, and IT University) buildings, with approx. 25.000 people in each sector.

Supporting the City and the Neighbourhood's effort to become green, healthy, and sustainable

Every city is struggling to transform cities to become in line with planetary boundaries. In Copenhagen Deputy Mayor, Line Barfod, has called for a shared effort to find new ways to solve the climate challenge that runs across segments in the cities. This is an open-ended task where all groups are invited. It is also of vast magnitude where all kinds of intelligence are needed.

The City of Copenhagen has decided to initiate a new paradigm of 'Local Traffic Plans' and include the public in developing these. The Local Councils of Amager are identified to be the first districts in Copenhagen where these will be developed. The goals of the first roll out are to:

- reduce CO2 emissions by increasing infrastructure for active travel modes
- increase road safety and reduce excessive speed, and
- limit heavy truck through-traffic in residential areas

As a supplement to the Municipality administered plan, the Local Council of Amager West seeks to expand the scope by adding a data driven documentation layer of actual conditions as a means to create a shared and documented baseline of knowledge in the discussion of the new plan.

The main instrument will be the public engagement of all people living, studying, and working in the district by engaging them into collect traffic data, stories and lived experiences from the consequences of a car centric economy. As such the project will also enact the Copenhagen Climate Plan 2035 and its focus on reducing consumption based emissions.

Miljøpunkt Amager will be the lead operator of the engagement plan. Miljøpunkt Amager is a local NGO with more than 20 years presence in the district with a mission to enact climate action in the district. Miljøpunkt Amager is organised as an independent fund but receives basic financial funding from City of Copenhagen and the two Copenhagen districts, situated on the island of Amager.

The scope and goal of this pilot project is to create a truly citizen-led local traffic infrastructure plan for the district of Amager Vest in Copenhagen.

The GREENGAGE Citizen Observatory in Copenhagen started from the political call to action to find new solutions and alternatives to fossil based behaviour. Since cities are complex systems with multiple stakeholders and interests, solutions need to take to account the plethora of perspectives from residents, companies, commuters etc. into a democratic process.

The overall vision for the GREENGAGE Citizen Observatory in Copenhagen is to align urban spaces with planetary boundaries while improving conditions for urban living. This includes to transform the neighbourhood with more places where people enjoy to spend time and interact with neighbours.

Objective 1: To test and investigate if citizen science and crowdsourced data collection can be utilised positively to engage citizens in local democratic dialogues in the pursuit of new solutions towards creating a climate-positive neighbourhood.

Objective 2: To use data collection to illuminate the existing lived experience and conditions in the neighbourhood as a baseline for generating citizens' ideas to where to improve the urban layout.

Objective 3: To use new digital solutions of data collection to understand citizens' needs for mobility, including local mobility, commuting mobility and access to the city in wider perspectives, and how integration into city planning processes can improve conditions.

The three objectives will be carried out by following these steps:

- Prepare the project - identify key stakeholders who will and can lead the vision for the neighbourhood forward.
- Establish a baseline - utilising access to cutting edge technologies the GREENGAGE project will establish a baseline collected by citizens to document existing living and environmental conditions in a manner where data are trustworthy and verifiable.
- Enable a shared dialogue - feedback loop to the neighbourhood on data and findings that is recognised by main stakeholders.
- From 'shared dialogue' actions are determined - prioritises key actions to follow and monitor.
- Plan the implementation - work to secure financing and political mandate for delivering long-term outcome.

7.4 Pilot Specification - Turano Valley, Italy

The Turano valley is located north-east of the city of Rome, on the first hills that rise about fifty kilometers from the urban settlement of the capital. It is bordered on its eastern side by the mountain range which can be considered as a continuation of the Simbruini mountains, i.e. that of the Carseolani mountains, which have the highest peak at 1,508 meters of Monte Navegna and on the western side by the eastern offshoots of the Sabine mountains, on average less elevated than the Carseolani. Other peaks higher than a thousand meters are Mount San Giovanni with its 1,201 meters, Mount Faito 1,227 meters, Mount Aquilone 1,337 meters and Mount Cervia at 1,436 meters. In the lower part of the valley, around the towns of Castel di Tora, Colle di Tora and Rocca Sinibalda, the harsher profiles of the mountain give way to the softer roundness of the hills. The average height is between 600 and 900 meters. The Turano Valley is home to 11 villages, which can be grouped on their geographical positioning within the valley:

- Villages overlooking Lake Turano: Ascrea, Castel di Tora, Colle di Tora and Paganico Sabino..
- Villages gravitating towards the "Via Salaria": Belmonte in Sabina..
- The innermost villages: Collalto Sabino, Collegiove, Longone Sabino, Nespolo, Rocca Sinibalda and Turania.

The valley is primarily characterized by Lake Turano, located at 536 m. above sea level, along the course of the Turano River which is about ten kilometres long and has a perimeter of about 36 km. The artificial basin created by the then Soc. Terni, between the years 1935-1939 through the construction of a dam over 80 meters high, which blocks a reservoir with a capacity of over 150 million cubic meters of water connected to the twin reservoir of Salto by an approximately 9 km long tunnel, whose waters serve to feed powerful hydroelectric plants which supply important industries, first of all those of Terni. The lake extends at the foot of the nature reserve of Mount Navegna/Cervia (1506 m), a nature reserve covered by woods, and is characterized by the presence on its shores of ancient villages and castles which are reflected in the clear waters.

The economy of the villages of the Valle del Turano is based on rural resources, on some craft businesses and on tourism. The Turano Valley area covers a geographical area of 322.14 km² and has 10,250 inhabitants (5,283 males and 4,967 females). A very high naturalistic and landscape value also corresponds to great difficulties deriving from the roughness of the territory and its morphology. The territorial context is also characterized by numerous other critical issues such as:

- Inadequacy of the road infrastructure system;
- Absence of integrated public transport for the connection of the Municipalities of the Area;
- The need for a broadband network both as a function of social equalization and with the aim of adapting territorial competitiveness to that of the rest of the regional territory
- Depopulation phenomena;
- Constant increase in the elderly population;
- Inadequacy of health services in the face of growing needs;
- Absence of job opportunities;
- Low income;

- Low level of schooling among the youth population;
- A constant growth of both "secular" and religious excursion tourism which requires an adequate supply of services.

The **pilot project** aims to directly address two of these critical challenges: the **inadequacy of the transport infrastructure** and the **progressive depopulation** of the area. Between 1951 and 2019, Italy lost approximately **289,000 residents** in villages with fewer than 10,000 inhabitants. The project supports a strategy of urban revitalization that calls for thoughtful territorial planning and better services.

This initiative aligns with two Green Deal priority areas:

- **Area 1: Increasing climate ambition – cross-sectoral challenges**
- **Area 10: Empowering citizens for the transition to a climate-friendly and sustainable Europe**

The GREENAGAGE Citizen Observatory in the Turano Valley supports the fight against depopulation and the improvement of territorial services by integrating:

- the analysis of data on mobility;
- support services to attract new residents;
- urban regeneration strategies co-designed with the community;
- Environment monitoring using Atmotube Pro, a portable air quality sensor distributed to local citizens.

Data is gathered through both satellite technologies and active citizen engagement, notably using the Atmotube Pro device to monitor air quality and microclimatic conditions. This integrated approach enhances understanding of the complex relationships between mobility patterns, environmental conditions, infrastructure, available services, and the dynamics of everyday social life.

The Observatory's objective is to support sustainable planning processes and promote smart, citizen-centred transport policies. Just an hour from Rome, the Turano Valley stands to benefit from the rise of remote working in the post-pandemic era, which has created new opportunities for repopulation and the revitalisation of smaller rural communities.

The initiative operates in close synergy with the national programme “Cultural and Social Regeneration of Small Historic Villages” (2022–2026), funded through the PNRR and led by the municipality of Paganico Sabino. Both actions share the strategic goal of reversing depopulation trends, improving quality of life, and strengthening the appeal of these villages through inclusive, data-informed decision-making.

Depopulation remains a structural challenge in rural Italy, with nearly 289,000 residents lost in villages with fewer than 10,000 inhabitants between 1951 and 2019. By combining mobility, environmental and socio-economic data, the Observatory contributes to the design of more targeted and effective regeneration strategies. The use of tools such as Atmotube Pro empowers citizens to take part in climate action and in shaping the future of their communities. In doing so, the Observatory directly contributes to the objectives of the European Green Deal, in particular those related to climate ambition and citizen empowerment.

7.5 Pilot Specification - Gerace, Italy

Gerace is an Italian town in the Province of Reggio Calabria, in the Region of Calabria. It is one of the most beautiful villages in Italy and extends over 28.6 km² and has 2,399 inhabitants, of which 1,202 males and 1,197 females. The population density is 97 inhabitants per km² in the municipality. In the vicinity of the municipalities of Agnana Calabria, Portigliola i Canolo, Gerace is located 46 km southeast of Vibo Valentia, the largest city in the vicinity. Situated at an altitude of 500 metres, the municipality of Gerace has the following geographical coordinates 38° 16' 16" North, 16° 13' 12" East. Gerace is a municipality in the Aspromonte National Park.

The pilot activity in Gerace builds on the opportunity to align with a mayor initiative already being implemented by the municipality: a 20-million regeneration programme funded by Next Generation EU Recovery and resilience Plan, contributing to the goals of the EU Green Deal for sustainable urban

regeneration. The GREENGAGE pilot will be implemented by 2026 and involve citizens in monitoring data relevant to the DNSH (Do No Significant Harm) principle.

The overall project called "Gerace, Door of the Sun" includes 9 integrated interventions to regenerate, repopulate and enhance the village's exceptional historic, artistic, cultural and social heritage making it a shared and living resource for both residents and visitors.

The GREENGAGE pilot action wants to combine Citizen Observatory data with satellite data to enhance the analytical capacity for the implementation of pilot area regeneration program. The overall work will aim at urban regeneration by developing a replicable system for DNSH.

The GREENGAGE pilot activities in Gerace directly align with the DNSH principle by prioritizing sustainable urban regeneration through environmentally responsible practices. By integrating Citizen Observatory data (e.g., air quality sensors and mobility analysis) with satellite imagery, the project ensures minimal environmental impact while addressing key local challenges. These efforts focus on improving air quality, enhancing infrastructure, and supporting decision-making with replicable solutions, all designed to prevent harm to ecosystems and adhere to the DNSH framework. More specifically, the relationship between the Citizens' Observatory and the application of the DNSH principle are:

- Air quality monitoring (through ATMOTUBE PRO sensors and web interface): Citizens collect data on polluting emissions and the presence of particulate matter. This data can support interventions to reduce emissions, respecting the DNSH by limiting air pollution.
- Mobility data collection (through Open data and Dashcam) identifying sustainable mobility methods are promoted, contributing to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions.
- Community awareness through inputs aimed at citizens increase environmental awareness and promote practices that respect the DNSH principle, such as waste reduction and the use of environmentally friendly means of transport.

The goals and objectives of this pilot project are to generate knowledge on how the increased awareness of citizens about the phenomena related to urban regeneration can contribute to a better and strengthened sustainable governance in a model medieval village, already member of the Most Beautiful Villages in Italy. This means that it meets the requirements relating to the specific ISO 9001 certification relating to "services aimed at enhancing, maintaining and recovering the national cultural heritage of memories and monuments, and at promoting tourism in the participating Municipalities". Considering the indicators established by the Do No Significant Harm (DNSH) principle which provide that the interventions envisaged by the national PNRR do not cause any significant damage to the environment, the project intends to support a citizens' observatory in monitoring the DNSH indicators so that the community can actively participate in monitoring and evaluating the impact of various activities and projects in their area and hold responsible parties accountable for any negative impacts. Citizens' observatories can provide valuable insights and data that can help decision-makers to identify and address any DNSH issues. Furthermore, the involvement of citizens in the monitoring process can promote transparency and accountability and increase community trust in decision-making processes.

The indicators considered of greatest interest to the community of the Municipality of Gerace are based both on the specific context conditions and on the basis of the project financed with a budget of 20 million euros from the PNRR and which is divided into 9 targeted interventions that will respond to the needs of the community and the visitor/tourist. First of all, at the context level, the importance of promoting awareness of the phenomena of hydrogeological instability is underlined considering the historical series recorded in the municipal area of Gerace (south-eastern Calabria) and the ability to analyse the risks of degradation of the historical-artistic heritage connected triggering these phenomena. The analysis of previous events and the current conditions of the inhabited centre carried out also considering the interventions carried out to protect the buildings, allows to draw indications on the most probable types of expected instability, in the various sectors of the inhabited area, on the occasion of extreme rain events and could provide a replicable model for other municipalities with similar morphological characteristics. Furthermore, on the basis of the "Gerace porta del sole" project, the prevailing values relating to the works envisaged in the inhabited centre can be monitored from the city observatory, favouring participatory environmental monitoring capable of including the monitoring of air quality and water, noise levels, waste management practices, biodiversity conservation and social impacts on local communities. Citizens can monitor and report these indicators through various means, such as surveys, sensor networks and community mapping exercises. Overall, the citizens' observatory to monitor DNSH indicators will be able to promote more inclusive and participatory decision-making

processes and improve the sustainability and resilience of the community, favoring the replicability of the experience in other villages in Italy and Europe.

Overall, supporting a citizens' observatory to monitor DNSH indicators can promote more inclusive and participatory decision-making processes and improve the sustainability and resilience of communities. An efficient system for the collection and analysis of the above-mentioned indicators could be considered in order to provide value-added participatory monitoring for territorial governance. The specific objectives of the pilot project can be summarized as:

- Develop a training activity aimed at training citizens and stakeholders who will join the Citizen Observatory;
- Develop a web application and interface that allows citizens to report values for relevant DNSH entries intuitively and securely.
- Collect, validate and aggregate data relating to DNSH indicators identified and linked to the works foreseen by the PNRR project through a secure and scalable back-end database and in a processing engine.
- Analyze and visualize aggregated data to generate insights and recommendations to improve the sustainable and inclusive governance system.
- Promote the altruistic work of citizens through recognition action, social networking features and feedback mechanisms and suggestions to incentivize citizens themselves to provide high-quality data
- Evaluate compliance with the municipal project planning.

The regeneration project in Gerace called "Gerace, door of the sun" has as its purpose the cultural, economic, and social regeneration of the village by focusing on the territorial identity which becomes a cultural attraction to build a model of economic development, a generator of employment and attractiveness residential. A series of interventions are envisaged aimed at the recovery and enhancement of buildings, at improving the accessibility of the village, at the provision of tourist, cultural and entertainment services, training and incentives for businesses. All these actions will have an impact not only on Gerace but throughout the Calabria Region.

8 GREENGAGE Innovation Pilots – Defining Governance

In this section, we summarise the existing and planned governance arrangements for each of the GREENGAGE Pilots, as outlined originally in Deliverable D2.4 (2023). The twin project objectives enhancing urban governance evidence-based decision-making and promoting citizen engagement in that process will be developed, deployed and fully demonstrated in 5 pilot engagements, in selected European cities and regions including: Bristol (the United Kingdom), the region of Noord Brabant (the Netherlands), Copenhagen (Denmark), and in both Turano and Gerace (Italy) (Figure 12). The aim to highlight the need for smart city governance by promoting citizen engagement, co-creation, gathering new data which complements existing datasets and evidence-based decision and policy making. Each of these innovation pilots target specific EU Green Deal objectives, specifically areas 1, 5, 8, 9 and 10.

Figure 12: GREENGAGE Governance Model

What follows for each of the innovation pilots including Bristol, Noord Brabant, Copenhagen as well as Turano and Gerace is a description of the existing governance process supported by diagrammatic representation of that process. The objective is to promote clearer understanding by identifying in detail existing urban planning decision-making and implementation process, and the potentials for introduction of Citizen Observatories derived intelligence for each pilot together with the added value of input from GREENGAGE tools.

8.1 Pilot Governance Model – Bristol, United Kingdom

For East Bristol Liveable Neighbourhood (EBLN), the **Project Team** and **Project Board** are already in place and have had the benefit of delivering the pilot Liveable Neighbourhood throughout the previous 18 months. The structure (Figure 13 and Figure 14) has worked effectively and has guided project development through the initial phases, shaping the community engagement and Outline Business Case.

The **Delivery Group** is responsible for each aspect of project delivery, drawing on the technical expertise of a wide range of Council services. The delivery group will report to project managers on a bi-weekly basis, who will then report to the **East Bristol Liveable Neighbourhood SRO**. The Project managers will be responsible for co-ordination and delivery of each work package, reporting to the Project Board on a monthly basis.

The Project Board will be led by the SRO and will assist the political champions with decision making and steering the delivery of the Liveable Neighbourhood programme. The Board itself is also made up of a diverse range of Council services to ensure that resources can be co-ordinated effectively.

Figure 13: East Bristol Liveable Neighbourhoods - Active Travel Process

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Figure 14: East Bristol Liveable Neighbourhoods – Project Management

8.2 Pilot Governance Model – North Brabant, The Netherlands

For the North Brabant pilot, Breda University of Applied Science (BUAS) and the Province of North Brabant (PNB) collaborate with a variety of partners. Whereas some partners facilitate the formation of Citizen Observatories, others provide technical or data support or facilitate mobility inquiries. Here the main relations between BUAS and PNB and other clusters are explained (Figure 15).

Project Partners - BUAS and PNB - together run the pilot. BUAS functions as project lead and supervises the project management, required frameworks, and technological embedding. PNB is the main client with a network of associated partners that can be involved in the formation of Citizen Observatories. BUAS sets up the necessary frameworks and methodologies to set up the pilot according to the PNB requirements. Within PNB it is primarily 'Team Fiets' that is responsible for the Citizen Observatories.

Governmental Partners - Next to PNB, the municipality of Heusden has also joined the pilot to assess their maintenance strategy. They wish to involve citizens more in their appraisal of maintenance of bike paths. Previously they worked solely with surveys, but Citizen Observatories could prove a more effective strategy. Additionally, within PNB the department of 'Regional Bike Paths' and 'Participation' are involved. Regional Bike Paths fulfils the same function as Heusden, only is in charge of the provincial bike paths instead of the local ones. The participation department is observing what Citizen Observatories can teach the Province about the inclusion of citizens in policy making through data gathering.

Technical Partners - Within the pilot, two technical partners support the North Brabant case. BUAS has worked together with Argaleo and its digital twin in other research projects and within education. The digital twin functions as decision making tool and PNB has a license for use. Simultaneously, the Fietsersbond and its web-based 'Bike Path Editor' provide a GPS based map wherein citizens can add physical obstacles when encountered.

Research Projects - PNB and BUAS together have already participated in research projects, together and separately, that deal with bicycle behaviour of citizens, including excluded groups, or discuss mobility behaviour through digital support. Some of the data gathered in these projects has also been

integrated into the Argaleo digital twin, or this tool has played a role in the projects. Some of the data from these projects and previous interactions with citizens can form a basis for the current pilot.

Fietsersbond- The largest volunteer biking organisation in the Netherlands with their own digital platform – the Fietsersbond Editor – wherein they objectively log the quality of bike paths in the Netherlands on 21 characteristics. The Fietsersbond is the main link to citizen observers due to their existing outreach. The motivation for the Fietsersbond is to improve the bike experience in the Netherlands, and through their data gathering activities, influence policy making. The Fietsersbond can highlight strategies for increased biking or reflect on the general accessibility of an area. These experts can offer relevant insights for Citizen Observatories and the data targets pursued by them.

Citizens - TCitizens use the bike consistently, or do not do so. Through the contacts of the Fietsersbond, or engagement campaigns by the Province or Municipality of Heusden, willing citizens can be onboarded to join the Citizen Observatory – a more intense involvement than the volunteering for the Fietsersbond. The members of the Citizen Observatory should be varied to gain layered insights into the decision-making process. This means including minorities or excluded groups, as well as different types of experts and functions. Employers, for instance, can play an important role in shaping the decision-making process to shift to sustainable transport through supporting bike use in workplaces.

Figure 15: North Brabant – Project Management

8.3 Pilot Governance Model – Ørestad, Denmark

Miljøpunkt Amager was and will be the lead operator of the engagement plan. Miljøpunkt Amager is a local NGO with more than 20 years presence in the district with a mission to enact climate action in the district. Miljøpunkt Amager is organised as an independent fund but receives basic financial funding from City of Copenhagen and the two Copenhagen districts on the island of Amager.

In contrast to the other pilots, the Copenhagen pilot is rooted in a citizen group rather than a governmental authority. The coordination between local interest groups is carried out through consultation and included in established processes, including regularly scheduled meetings with mayor’s office, alignment processes with traffic department, board meetings in MPA and Local Council Amager Vest and ad hoc alignment discussions between secretariat employees. The main interest groups in district are: City Hall - The citizens’ representative legislative body of Municipality of

Copenhagen, governed by a Lord Mayor and 6 deputy mayors. 55 elected members. The relevant deputy mayor is Line Barfod, Mayor of Technical and Environmental Affairs (Figure 16).

Amager Vest Local Council - Ørestad lies within the district of Amager Vest. An elected local council has local authority, including the mandate to drive the environmental and climate forward. Local Council of Amager Vest delegates (together with the Local Council of Amager East) this responsibility to Miljøpunkt Amager.

OICC, 'Ørestad Innovation City, Copenhagen' - the companies' resident in Ørestad as well as building Investors are organised in collaboration to increase innovation in new urban solutions, focusing on climate change mitigation.

GFS - The residential building association is maintaining the part of area that is not under municipal maintenance. GFS coordinates between municipality, investors, and residential building owners. GFS is an amalgamation of all smaller building associations in Ørestad.

Miljøpunkt Amager MPA - is a community driven NGO focusing on climate and environment, especially to support the city's goals to become climate neutral. MPA is organised as an independent fund with an independent governing board, and receives some partial funding from two local councils, and altruistic funds.

Figure 16. Copenhagen Pilot Project Management

8.4 Pilot Governance Model - Turano Valley, Italy

The scheme represents the governance model adopted for the pilot activity at the Turano Valley, in the Lazio Region (IT) coordinated by Borghi più Belli d'Italia (BBI). It is designed to address the main sustainable challenges identified by the project (Figure 17).

It is based on the "quintuple helix" model, which supports social innovation by recognising the active roles of both organised civil society and informal citizen groups, and by promoting smart specialisation and innovation in rural and heritage areas.

The governance framework brings together a broad set of actors, categorised by their role and influence on the territory:

Government – constituted by the authorities and institutions that influence the territory and represent the sphere of political influence and that owns the capital of regulatory knowledge and (are mentioned here in specify: Borghi Italia which coordinates the pilot, ANCI Lazio, the Lazio Region, the Province of Rieti, ASTRAL the company of the Lazio Region responsible for the Design, Construction, Maintenance, Administrative Management of about 1,500 kilometres of Road Network Regional, and finally, the 16 municipalities or villages located in the Valle del Turano area).

Economic system – represented by local companies and industries, utilities, and any larger companies, national, European, international that may have some influence on the local economic system.

Media/Public – represented by the actors that make up the social and information capital, from local citizens to non-profit associations to citizens' committees, up to the media, local newspapers, as well as tourists and regional, national and international media that can influence the territory.

Educational system – represented by research centres and universities that gravitate in the territory for studies and research and those that may have interest in it at a potential level.

The participatory process envisioned by the GREENGAGE project follows 3 key phases, namely:

Activation phase of the process (after the development of the methodology used for the pilot activity) which is characterised by the work for stakeholder involvement, inviting the communities identified in the stakeholder mapping to be part of the City Observatory.

- Design and co-creation phase characterised by two main stages. The first was a **preliminary co-exploration phase**, which focused on testing the pilot's broad objectives, methodologies, and data needs. Following this, the second stage began after the **Ideathon held in March 2025**, which marked a turning point in the project's co-creation process.

During and after the Ideathon, partner organizations worked intensively to further develop and refine the **GREENGAGE App**, improving its functionalities and user interface based on participant feedback and identified needs. Similarly, work progressed on the **Copernicus data visualization platform**, which will provide synthesis examples and storytelling on key pilot area themes such as mobility, air quality, and attractiveness. This collaborative effort ensured that the app became a practical and user-friendly tool for environmental monitoring and citizen engagement, aligned with the DNSH principle and the specific goals of urban regeneration.

The Ideathon also strengthened stakeholder commitment and helped finalize data collection protocols and engagement strategies to maximize the app's impact during the implementation phase. A Final phase features a closing event to illustrate the results achieved, to show the usefulness of datasets to support decisions for the fields of policy, science, and technology and to thank all stakeholders involved for their commitment and contribution. The GREENGAGE App will also be promoted as a tool for ongoing participatory monitoring in line with local regeneration goals.

A transversal activity is represented by the monitoring activity to supervise all planned activities and to make sure that they are carried out as planned.

TURANO VALLEY AND THE SUBSYSTEMS OF THE QUINTUPLE HELIX MODEL

Figure 17: Turano Project Management

8.5 Pilot Governance Model - Gerace, Italy

The scheme represents the governance model for the pilot activity in the city of Gerace, Calabria Region (IT) proposed by Borghi più Belli d'Italia (BBI) and aimed at addressing the challenges for sustainable development set by GREENGAGE (Figure 18).

To develop the Pilot Governance Model graphic, the "quintuple helix" framework was adopted, which fosters social innovation by recognising and valuing both the roles of, emphasizing and giving dignity and autonomous consideration both to the role played by organized civil society and the "unorganized or informal civil society" highlighting their significance in smart specialization and innovation processes within rural territories.

Since the pilot activity is concentrated exclusively in the territory of the Municipality of Gerace, a pentagon-shaped graphic representation was chosen to highlight in a simple way the governance proposed according to the five-fold helix model characterized by the following sets of actors:

Government – represented by the authorities and institutions that influence the territory and represent the sphere of political influence and that possesses the capital of normative knowledge and have been specifically identified in particular: Borghi Italia which coordinates the pilot, the Province of Reggio Calabria, the Calabria Region, the Municipality of Gerace which manages the project "Gerace, porta del sole" funded by PNRR.

Economic system – represented by local companies grouped in informal associations of traders "Siamo Tutti Ruggero" and "Il Borgo Incantato", by utilities and by any larger companies, national, European, international that may have some influence on the local economic system.

Media/Public – represented by the actors that make up the social and information capital, from the citizens of the territory to the non-profit associations to the citizens' committees present in the territory: "Leggendo tra le righe" Association; "Proloco" of Gerace (Association promoting local culture and tourism), up to the media, local newspapers ("City Now" and "Lente Locale"), the National Association "Touring Club" which awarded the "Bandiera Arancione" to the territory of Gerace and assigned to localities that not only enjoy a valuable historical, cultural and environmental heritage, but are able to

offer tourists a quality welcome; as well as tourists and regional, national and international media that can influence the territory.

Educational system – represented by research centers and universities that gravitate in the territory for studies and research and those that may have interest in it at a potential level. In particular, at the local level the nearest structures are the University for Foreigners Dante Alighieri of Reggio Calabria and the University of Mediterranean Studies of Reggio Calabria.

Figure 18: Gerace Project Management

9 Establishing a Citizen Observatory

Effective governance of Citizen Observatories requires coordination across multiple domains including technology and data governance, community engagement, ethical oversight, and policy alignment. However, establishing a Citizen Observatory is a context-sensitive process that can vary widely across organisations, cities, and projects. These variations stem from differences in institutional frameworks, stakeholder dynamics, and local priorities. To support organisations in navigating this complexity, and drawing on practical insights from the GREENGAGE project, we present a generalised Pilot Owner Journey (Figure 19). This journey diagram outlines the key stages, processes, and activities involved in setting up and operating a Citizen Observatory. It serves not only as a practical implementation guide but also as a foundational tool for governance. By clarifying activities, decision points, and activities where stakeholder interactions are expected, the journey helps pilot owners establish transparent and accountable structures for managing observatories.

The journey progresses through a series of key processes. For simplicity, iterative activities and specific roles or swimlanes are not depicted. The "GREEN Engine" refers to the suite of GREENGAGE technologies and tools. However, it is not always necessary to rely exclusively on these tools. Pilot owners may already have access to existing technologies that are better suited to their specific onboarding needs and piloting activities. For example, the North Brabant pilot utilises another mobile application to engage participants and collect mobility data, along with a digital twin platform for data analysis and visualisation. Similarly, the Bristol pilot used the Commonplace platform to support user engagement for the East Bristol Liveable Neighbourhood initiative. The processes represented in the figure are explained below.

The **Situational Screening Requirements** process serves as the foundation for the pilot, providing a structured assessment of the context, objectives, and feasibility. It begins with an exploration of thematic areas and research questions, grounded in local issues or political priorities that may influence the pilot's direction. Once the area of interest is selected, clear objectives and goals are defined to ensure a shared understanding of purpose.

This stage also involves identifying data gaps and developing a stakeholder engagement strategy to secure the alignment and support necessary for the successful deployment of GREENGAGE tools and technologies, which are instrumental in enabling evidence-based decision-making.

Following this, appropriate GREENGAGE technologies and/or external tools are selected to ensure alignment between the pilot's objectives and the digital solutions for data collection, analysis, and visualisation. As a best practice, a data registry should be established to document the datasets to be collected and identify the individuals or teams responsible for their management.

The process culminates in the development of an onboarding and training strategy, which includes ethical considerations such as participant consent, information sheets, privacy policies, and training materials. These are prepared and shared with participants to ensure transparency and compliance.

As a foundational step, this process informs and shapes all subsequent phases of the pilot journey.

The **Citizen Observatory (CO) Pre-Piloting** process is focused on establishing a robust operational framework for the pilot. It begins by inviting selected stakeholders and users to participate, with the aim of identifying strengths and limitations that can be addressed prior to the full-scale rollout.

Participants who express interest undergo an onboarding process that includes ethical procedures such as providing informed consent. These procedures adhere to data management standards for handling personal data, including pseudonymisation or anonymisation, and a data registry is maintained to track the types of data collected during the pilot.

While ethical protocols are enforced, participants also receive multiple training sessions, covering both the concept of a Citizen Observatory and the practical use of GREENGAGE tools. The piloting campaign then proceeds to collect data through various experiments.

This is a continuous process, with several activities running in parallel to allow new observers to join at different stages. Feedback from participants, preliminary evaluations, and lessons learned offer valuable insights that help refine the GREENGAGE tools and, where necessary, adapt the thematic focus.

This phase is critical to ensuring the success and effectiveness of the full-scale piloting effort.

CO Setup or Situational Screening/Roadmapping

CO Pre-Piloting

Piloting

Evaluation/Impact Assessment

Pilot Owners Use GREENGAGE Outcomes

Figure 19: A Pilot Owner journey.

The full-scale **Piloting** process marks the implementation phase of the pilot missions (or experiments). It begins with the official launch, using a variety of communication channels tailored to the specific piloting context. Onboarding and ethical procedures are applied to ensure proper consent documentation and data management practices are in place. Participants also receive training on the Citizen Observatory concept and the use of GREENGAGE technologies, equipping them to begin data collection activities.

Observers are engaged through multiple methods, including workshops, focus group discussions, surveys, local walks, interviews, and the use of GREENGAGE tools. Please note that, where appropriate, alternatives to GREENGAGE tools may be used to avoid potential bottlenecks, for example, when users are already registered on another platform or when pilot owners are leveraging tools from existing initiatives. As these activities unfold, the data registry is continuously updated to reflect ongoing contributions. Collected data is uploaded to secure storage systems for further analysis and visualisation, with privacy safeguards in place to ensure data is pseudonymised or anonymised as required.

Both GREENGAGE and external tools may be used to interpret the data, which is then compiled into reports. These reports offer valuable insights into the performance of the pilot and support the evaluation process.

This phase represents the operational core of the pilot journey, directly reflecting the effectiveness of the planning and preparatory stages.

The **Evaluation and Impact Assessment** process focuses on measuring the outcomes of the pilot and identifying opportunities for improvement. Running in parallel with the piloting phase, it begins by reviewing the mission objectives and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) in relation to the results achieved.

Participants are invited to take part in various evaluation activities, including questionnaires, surveys, interviews, and usability testing. A data register is maintained to track contributions from different piloting teams.

The collected data is analysed to assess the status before and after the implementation of GREENGAGE tools, offering a comparative view of impact. Insights from this analysis are documented, culminating in the development of a White Book that captures lessons learned and provides policy recommendations. This process supports continuous improvement and helps prepare the pilot for potential scaling or refinement.

The **Pilot Owners Use GREENGAGE Outcomes** process focuses on leveraging the results from the piloting, evaluation, and impact assessment phases. The goal is to apply the insights and lessons learned to similar initiatives, the development of new observatories, contributions to policy assessment and formulation, and evidence-based planning and decision-making.

These high-impact activities are closely linked to the Situational Screening process, where the original objectives of the pilot were defined. By aligning outcomes with initial goals, this process ensures that the knowledge gained is effectively translated into broader applications and long-term value.

In summary, the Pilot Owner journey typically begins with community engagement and capacity building, participants undergo training in scientific methods, data ethics, and tool usage through the GREENGAGE Academy's onboarding framework. Once the community is ready, co-exploration workshops help define locally relevant themes (such as air quality or mobility), identify data gaps, and design sensing missions that blend open data sources (Copernicus, municipal datasets) with citizen-gathered inputs. Equipped with apps, low-cost sensors and platforms like the GREENGAGE DataHub and GREEN Engine, citizen observers collect, visualize and analyse data in real time. Alongside data campaigns, structured feedback loops foster ongoing dialogue between observers and public authorities, ensuring that findings directly inform decision-making. This holistic, iterative pathway transforms Citizen Observatories into dynamic governance instruments, grounded in local realities yet interconnected by shared methodologies and technological platforms, capable of generating both community empowerment and policy impact across diverse urban and rural contexts. While the establishment of Citizen Observatories may encounter practical challenges, especially in rural or less digitally connected areas (as we observed in GREENGAGE pilots), they still hold the potential to act as catalysts for local engagement and cross-sector collaboration. This potential is more likely to emerge when appropriate tools are made available and when training is carefully tailored to the needs and capacities of diverse stakeholders. In this sense, the Observatory becomes more than a data collection initiative - it can gradually evolve into a shared

platform that supports open dialogue, strengthens trust, and fosters co-responsibility in local governance.

AWAITING VALIDATION BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

10 Conclusions

This report has sought to build on our original submission D2.4 (2023). It has noted the imperative for a reformed system of smart urban governance (one that emphasises multi-level, collaborative and inclusive action and exploits digital advances to the full) to respond to the challenges set out in the European Green Deal. The threats posed by climate change are of an unprecedented complexity, best captured in the heuristic of the “wicked issue”. Central to this proposition are the competing ideological and normative beliefs that inform the interpretations of these challenges, and the responses to them, held by the multiple stakeholders that any effective inclusive action must implicate. These differences are most effectively challenged through a process of dialogue between partners, including the public. The multi-faceted nature and scope of this grand challenge can best be understood through a strategy informed by “systems thinking”. This implies a preoccupation with holism; one that recognises the need for top down, bottom up and transversal integration of governance. The past two decades have witnessed an IT-enabled explosion in citizen science activity in which the public participate actively in the gathering and analysis of data. The Citizen Observatory model extend this logic to implicate citizens in the formulation of (collaboratively generated) evidence-based policy too. This innovative approach has undoubted potential. The GREENGAGE project provides various means for achieving this potential in the five pilot areas and beyond. In this report, we articulate a diagrammatic pilot owner “journey” to assist local policy makers and project managers to establish Citizen Observatories. This is flexible and adaptable to different circumstances, reflecting the diverse urban and rural contexts of our pilot areas. And the “situated experimentation” methodology adopted by GREENGAGE more broadly.

To conclude, Citizen Observatories represent a promising approach to enhancing urban and territorial governance by fostering inclusive, participatory, and evidence-based decision-making processes. Their potential is maximised when appropriate technologies are provided from the outset, coupled with ongoing support for data analysis and interpretation. This combination enables Observatories not only to collect valuable information but also to generate actionable insights that drive growth and improvement for the community. Although implementation challenges may arise, particularly in less connected or resource-constrained areas, tailored tools and capacity-building initiatives can significantly strengthen their impact. By bridging local knowledge with scientific data and facilitating multi-stakeholder collaboration, Observatories have the potential to contribute to more resilient and adaptive governance models aligned with sustainable development and climate action goals. Their continued evolution as living platforms for engagement and co-creation is essential for realising the transformative potential of citizen science within the GREENGAGE framework and beyond.

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